

Natural processes and biotechnological innovation in photosynthesis

Pre-scientific paper by
Adrien Reiser
Klasse 8B

Betreut durch Lukas Hutter, DPhil

February 16, 2026
BG/BRG St. Martin Villach
St. Martiner Straße 7
9500 Villach

Preface

Being naturally interested in both chemistry and biology, I wanted to write and expand my knowledge on a topic that touches both of these subjects. Being both aware and impressed by the complexity of the processes underpinning photosynthesis, the motivation to learn more about this phenomenon made me choose it as a topic for my pre-scientific paper. Not only did I want to explore the biochemical functions of photosynthesis, but I also aimed to combine the topic with other interesting research questions. I was intrigued by artificial approaches of replicating photosynthesis for means of capturing CO₂ or generating energy, which is why I chose to dive deeper into the applications of photosynthesis in biotechnology. As many modern artificial photosynthetic systems require genetic engineering, I decided to also write about the basics of CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing. Being aware of both the power of such technologies and the societal implications it might have, I wanted to conclude my paper with an outlook on potential applications of enhanced photosynthesis, as well as contrasting it with ethical concerns and current legislation in Austria.

Villach, February 16, 2026

Adrien Reiser

Abstract

Englisch

In this prescientific paper, I aim to investigate the chemical processes underlying both the light and dark phase of photosynthesis in depth, and to explore its biological sites and evolution. In the section on the light stage of photosynthesis, I investigate each step of the process while also considering processes besides linear electron transfer (like ATP synthesis or cyclic electron transfer). In the section on the light-independent phase of photosynthesis I highlight the differences between C3, C4, and CAM plants and also discuss processes not directly related to the Calvin-Benson cycle. Then, I aim to introduce the field of artificial photosynthesis, discussing its functioning as well as its application. Finally, I explore methods of genetic engineering and other approaches through which photosynthesis can be improved, building on the knowledge acquired earlier on natural photosynthesis and considering applications of enhanced photosynthesis as well as ethical concerns and the legal structure in Austria for genomics research.

Abstract

Deutsch

In dieser vorwissenschaftlichen Arbeit untersuche ich die chemischen Prozesse, die sowohl der lichtabhängigen als auch der lichtunabhängigen Phase der Photosynthese zugrunde liegen im Detail und beleuchte zudem ihre biologischen Lokalisierungen sowie ihre Evolution. Im Abschnitt der lichtabhängigen Reaktionen analysiere ich jeden Schritt des Prozesses und berücksichtige dabei auch Vorgänge außerhalb des linearen Elektronentransfers (wie ATP-Synthese oder zyklischer Elektronentransfer). Im Abschnitt zur lichtunabhängigen Phase der Photosynthese hebe ich die Unterschiede zwischen C3-, C4- und CAM-Pflanzen hervor und bespreche außerdem Prozesse, die nicht direkt mit dem Calvin-Benson-Zyklus zusammenhängen. Anschließend beleuchte ich das Gebiet der künstlichen Photosynthese und erläutere sowohl ihre Funktionsweise als auch ihre Anwendungsmöglichkeiten. Abschließend untersuche ich Methoden der Gentechnik und weitere Ansätze zur Verbesserung der Effizienz der Photosynthese, basierend auf dem zuvor erarbeiteten Wissen zur natürlichen Photosynthese, und betrachte dabei sowohl mögliche Anwendungen einer optimierten Photosynthese als auch ethische Fragestellungen und den rechtlichen Rahmen in Österreich für genomische Forschung.

Contents

1	Introduction to photosynthesis	1
1.1	Definition and biological significance	1
1.2	Types of photosynthesis	1
1.3	Evolutionary origins of photosynthesis	2
1.4	Oxygenic photosynthesis	3
2	Light reactions: Photochemical pathways	4
2.1	Overview	4
2.2	Step 1: Light absorption	5
2.2.1	The photosystem (PSII)	5
2.2.2	Pigment molecules:	5
2.2.3	Excitation states:	8
2.3	Step 2: Electronic excitation energy transmission between pigment molecules	8
2.3.1	Förster-type transfer in the weak-coupling limit	9
2.3.2	Delocalised EET	10
2.3.3	The role of the environment	10
2.4	Step 3: Arriving at the center: 'The special pair'	10
2.5	Step 4: electron transfer chain in PSII on acceptor side	11
2.6	Step 5: electron transfer chain on donor side in PSII	13
2.6.1	Overview	13
2.6.2	Oxygen-evolving complex (OEC)	13
2.6.3	S-state cycle	13
2.7	Step 6: Cytochrome b_6f and the Q-cycle	15
2.7.1	Core function of cytochrome b_6f	15
2.7.2	Structure of $cytb_6f$	15
2.7.3	The Q-cycle (overview)	16
2.7.4	Half-cycle 1: oxidation of PQH_2 at Q_o/Q_p site and creation of semiquinone on the n-side	16

2.8	Step 7: Plastocyanine and delivery to PSI	19
2.8.1	Pc with its Copper	19
2.8.2	Reduction of Pc by cytochrome b_6f	19
2.8.3	Diffusion through the thylakoid lumen	19
2.8.4	Luminal docking to PSI	19
2.9	Step 8: PSI and the reduction of ferredoxin	20
2.9.1	Structure of PSI	20
2.9.2	Light absorption	20
2.9.3	Electron transfer chain on acceptor side	20
2.10	Step 9: Ferredoxin-NADP ⁺ reductase (FNR)	21
2.10.1	Structure and binding	21
2.10.2	Overall reaction	21
2.10.3	Why an FAD intermediate is needed	22
2.10.4	Stepwise redox sequence at FNR (FAD states and naming)	22
2.10.5	Proton source	22
2.11	Intermezzo: Cyclic electron transfer	23
2.12	Step 10: ATP synthesis	24
2.12.1	Structure	24
2.12.2	CF1: catalytic head (where ATP is formed)	26
2.12.3	CF0: membrane motor (how the proton gradient drives rotation)	26
2.12.4	Stoichiometry	26
3	Dark reactions: Carbon fixation	27
3.1	Calvin-Benson Cycle (C3)	27
3.1.1	Overview	27
3.1.2	Carboxylation	29
3.1.3	Reduction	29
3.1.4	Regeneration of RuBP	30
3.1.5	Stoichiometry	34
3.1.6	The competing reaction: Oxygenation (photorespiration)	34
3.2	C4 pathway	34

3.3	CAM pathway	35
3.4	GAP to carbohydrates (sucrose and starch)	36
3.4.1	Overview: linking GAP production to end-product synthesis	36
3.4.2	Export	36
3.4.3	Sucrose synthesis (cytosol)	36
3.4.4	Starch synthesis (chloroplast stroma)	37
3.4.5	Regulation	37
3.4.6	Avoiding unnecessary cycling: FBPase	37
4	Biological sites of photosynthesis	38
5	Artificial photosynthesis	40
5.1	Going artificial	40
5.2	Introduction	40
5.3	Definition and scope	40
5.4	Classification of artificial photosynthetic approaches	41
5.5	Photochemical artificial photosynthesis	41
5.5.1	Logic & definition	41
5.5.2	Engineering setup	42
5.5.3	Chemical reactions	42
5.6	Biophotovoltaics	42
5.6.1	Logic and definition	42
5.6.2	Origin of electrons from H ₂ O	43
5.6.3	Intracellular electron transport and leakage points	43
5.6.4	Mediator-based electron transfer	43
5.7	Biohybrid and semi-artificial photosynthesis	44
5.7.1	Logic and definition	44
5.7.2	Mechanism	44
6	Genetic engineering and its applications in photosynthesis	46
6.1	Fundamentals of Genetic Engineering	46
6.1.1	Recombinant DNA techniques and gene editing	46

6.1.2	Repair mechanisms	47
6.1.3	Gene expression regulation and promoter systems	50
6.1.4	Chloroplast vs. nuclear genome transformation	51
6.2	Strategies for improving photosynthetic efficiency	51
6.2.1	RuBisCo optimisation	51
6.2.2	Broader light absorption spectrum	52
6.2.3	Altering pigment concentration	53
6.2.4	Overcoming photorespiration	53
6.2.5	Synthetic carbon fixation pathways (e.g., CETCH cycle, im- plementing C4 in C3 plants)	54
6.3	Applications	54
6.3.1	Higher yield in food and feed crops and nutritional make-up .	54
6.3.2	Side-effect of improving research beneficial to other fields of science	55
6.3.3	Water-limited agriculture	55
6.3.4	Increased CO ₂ capture for green cities and climate change . .	55
6.4	Dangers and disadvantages	55
6.4.1	Gene flow	55
6.4.2	Antibiotic resistance	56
6.4.3	Uncertainty over long-term effects	56
6.5	Regulation on genetic engineering	57
6.5.1	EU environmental release framework	57
6.5.2	EU post-authorisation environmental monitoring	57
6.5.3	EU 0.9% threshold	57
6.5.4	Gentechnikgesetz (Austria)	57
6.5.5	Summary	58
6.6	Ethical discussion: genetic engineering and biotechnological innova- tion in photosynthesis	58
7	Conclusion	60
	References	61

1 Introduction to photosynthesis

1.1 Definition and biological significance

Photosynthesis is the process by which green plants and certain other organisms transform light energy into chemical energy. During photosynthesis in green plants, light energy is captured and used to convert water, carbon dioxide, and minerals into oxygen and energy-rich organic compounds. (Lambers & Bassham, 2025)

1.2 Types of photosynthesis

Organisms have evolved several strategies for harvesting light energy. When detailing the chemical processes of 'photosynthesis', I will focus on the light phase of oxygenic photosynthesis and on the dark phases of C3, C4 and CAM plants. (Kent, 2000)

The first categorisation of photosynthesis is the differentiation between oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis. In oxygenic photosynthesis, H_2O acts as the electron donor and O_2 is the product, while H_2S / H_2 / Fe^{2+} or other organic compounds are used in anoxygenic photosynthesis as electron donors. (Blankenship, 2021)

Secondly, photosynthesis can be characterised by its light-harvesting strategy, more specifically the molecules used to absorb photons. Most oxygenic phototrophs use chlorophyll a (and other chlorophyll molecules) as pigments. Bacteriochlorophyll-based photosynthesis uses bacteriochlorophyll, common in anoxygenically photosynthesising bacteria, which allows for the absorption of longer wavelengths. (Blankenship, 2021)

A final classification is contrasting photosynthesis by its carbon fixation pathway, differentiating between C3, C4 or CAM photosynthesis. In C3 photosynthesis, CO_2 is fixed by RuBisCo and the first product is a 3-carbon compound (hence the name). Most plants use this pathway. In C4 photosynthesis, CO_2 is fixed into a 4-carbon compound and there is a spatial separation of the CO_2 fixation and the Calvin cycle. Maize, sugarcane and tropical grasses are some proponents of this method. In CAM photosynthesis, there is a time gap between the intake of CO_2 and its fixation. This

is more common in arid regions and cacti and pineapples photosynthesise that way. (Kent, 2000)

1.3 Evolutionary origins of photosynthesis

Photosynthesis is the only major biological process that converts solar energy into stable chemical energy, supplying organisms with the energy they need through complex food webs. Multiple lines of evidence indicate that photosynthesis is an ancient metabolism that arose relatively early in the history of the Earth. Geological and isotopic data suggest that phototrophic organisms existed by around 3.2 to 3.5 billion years ago. The oldest known fossils are 3.7 billion years old. This suggests photosynthesis may have emerged relatively early after life began, though the exact timing remains debated. These early forms of photosynthesis were almost certainly anoxygenic, using electron donors such as hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) rather than water. Today, anoxygenic phototrophs include several bacterial groups, such as green sulfur bacteria, purple bacteria, heliobacteria, and filamentous anoxygenic phototrophs. Oxygenic photosynthesis originated from bacteria and later diversified through a complex evolutionary history involving extensive horizontal gene transfer, meaning that photosynthetic traits were exchanged between organisms rather than inherited along a single lineage. This makes the study of the evolution of photosynthesis much harder. Chloroplasts, for instance, are thought to have evolved through the endosymbiosis of cyanobacteria with eukaryotes. (Blankenship, 2010)

To better study the evolution of photosynthetic systems, I will examine each part of it individually, even if different subsystems are inevitably intertwined.

Reaction centers, the core complexes driving photochemistry, appear to have evolved from a single ancestor and diverged into two main types, type I and type II (PSI and PSII). Known anoxygenic phototrophs typically possess only one of these, whereas oxygenic phototrophs such as cyanobacteria or plants have both, enabling the oxidation of water (and thus the production of O_2). The fusion theory (Xiong, Fischer, Inoue, Nakahara, & Bauer, 1998) argues that the two types of reaction centers developed independently and then merged. In contrast, the selective loss

theory argues that at first both types of reaction centers were present and that some organisms lost one of them over time (Olson, 2004).

Light-harvesting antenna systems and carbon fixation pathways show far greater evolutionary diversity, having independently evolved multiple times by different organisms. This suggests that early phototrophs were likely photoheterotrophic (ie. they didn't necessarily use CO_2) and only later acquired the ability to fix inorganic carbon. (Blankenship, 2010; University of Chicago, 2022)

1.4 Oxygenic photosynthesis

"Oxygenic photosynthesis is a light-driven process in which H_2O is oxidized to O_2 , and electrons released are used for nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) and ferredoxin reduction. Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is then produced from the protons (H^+) released in water oxidation, and those that are transported across the photosynthetic membranes by proton pumps." (Lamb et al., 2022)

2 Light reactions: Photochemical pathways

2.1 Overview

Figure 1: Graphical overview of noncyclic and cyclic electron transfer in chloroplasts. (Cherepanov et al., 2017)

At the beginning of the light phase of photosynthesis, pigment-protein antennae in the thylakoid membrane absorb photons and transfer the excitation energy as excitons to the reaction centers of PSII (P680) and PSI (P700, covered later). Charge separation takes place in PSII and an electron travels along the acceptor chain of pheophytin, Q_A and Q_B while reducing plastoquinone to plastoquinol. The oxidised reaction center is reduced again (so the process can be repeated) by electrons from H_2O , which in turn are extracted at the oxygen-evolving complex (OEC) and the Mn-Ca cluster. The oxidation of H_2O (4 cycles) produces O_2 and releases protons into the lumen (contributing to a H^+ gradient). Plastoquinol transports the electron and transfers them to cytochrome b_6f , which in turn transfers its electrons to plastocyanine via the Q-cycle and once again pumps H^+ across the thylakoid

membrane. Plastocyanine brings the electrons to PSI, where another light-driven charge separation brings the electron to ferredoxin, following another chain of redox reactions. Ferredoxin-NADP⁺ reductase (also known as FNR) produces NADPH from the reduced ferredoxin and NADP⁺, oxidising the ferredoxin so it can be reduced again by PSI. The proton gradient built up by the charge separation and cytochrome *b₆f* is used by ATP synthase to make ATP from ADP and phosphate (Pi). Cyclic electron transfer is an alternative route which allows the chloroplast to shift its NADPH:ATP ratio by redirecting electron from ferredoxin back to the plastoquinone pool via PGR5/PRGL1 or NDH routes, thus pumping more H⁺ without net NADPH production, leading to a higher ATP concentration, though this process is not well understood yet.

A graphical overview of the processes of the light phase of oxygenic photosynthesis can be seen under Figure 1.

2.2 Step 1: Light absorption

2.2.1 The photosystem (PSII)

The photosystem, located in the thylakoid membrane of the chloroplast, is the functional protein unit that uses light energy to excite an electron and ultimately initiate the electron transport chain. It consists of a reaction center, where charge separation happens, and antennae, which collect photons. On the outside of the antennae, so-called light harvesting complexes (LHC's), pigment-protein complexes, aim to absorb light efficiently. Pigment molecules hit by photons are brought to an 'excited state', where they have an excess of energy that will be given off shortly after excitation as the transfer of an 'exciton' and later through the passing on of electrons, initiating the chain reaction of the Z-scheme.

2.2.2 Pigment molecules:

The most famous pigment molecules are the chlorophylls and carotenoids. In cyanobacteria and some algae, bilins also play a big role. What they have in common is an alternating single-double bond and pi electron system (porphyrin ring). Their

Figure 2: *Molecular structures of chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b.*
Note. Reprinted from (OpenStax, 2018)

molecular structure can be seen in Figure 2.

Pigment molecules can absorb a bandwidth of wavelengths (not a discrete, specific wavelength) thanks to their molecular structure. Multiple possible substituents (side-groups) shift energy levels slightly. Delocalised electrons in the ring allow a photon to excite an electron from the pi to pi* if the photon's energy match an allowed energy gap. In addition to this, a single molecule has several vibrational sublevels. Vibrations are bond stretches and compressions within the molecules, angles bending, twisting etc. These vibrations are quantised ($v=0$, $v=1$, $v=2$, etc.). A molecule at ground state has its discrete vibration levels, while an excited molecule also has its discrete, different from ground state, vibration levels. All of this creates absorption bands (not lines) where multiple wavelengths of energy can be absorbed by a single pigment molecule. In addition to that, LHC's contain a multitude of different pigment molecules, which allows for wide absorption spectra. The absorption spectra of β -carotene, chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b can be seen in Figure 3.

The perceived colour of plants comes from their pigments. Chlorophylls absorb primarily blue and red wavelengths, which is why they appear green to us (they

reflect the green light, as this is the wavelength which absorbs the least). Similarly, carotenoids appear red/yellow as they primarily absorb blue light.

In autumn, chlorophyll is the first pigment molecule to be broken down, which is why leaves turn orange (the relative amount of carotenoids to chlorophylls rises)

Figure 3: Absorption spectrum and action spectrum (actual photochemical efficiency) of major photosynthetic pigments.

Note. Reprinted from (Henke & Buck-Sorlin, 2017)

2.2.3 Excitation states:

The energy needed to excite chlorophyll from S_0 (ground state) to S_1 (first excited state) is roughly that of a photon of wavelength of red light. To excite it directly from S_0 to S_2 blue-light wavelength photons are needed. This is why absorption peaks can be observed for visible light of these two wavelengths (blue and red). Once excited to S_2 , the chlorophyll quickly moves down to S_1 excitation level via molecular vibration (internal conversion). Once at S_1 excitation level, the chlorophyll molecule has several options to give off its energy:

- emit a photon. This causes fluorescence and is not advantageous to the chloroplast.
- lose the excess energy as heat (internal conversion), which also does not benefit the chloroplast.
- excitation energy transfer (EET): if another pigment molecule is nearby, in the correct position, orientation and energy level, non-radiative exchange of energy can take place. In this case, the excitation energy is transferred from pigment molecule to pigment molecule (it is said that the 'exciton' travels) until it reaches the reaction center and can be used to perform charge separation in the oxygen-evolving complex to power the initiation of the electron transfer chain of redox reactions.

2.3 Step 2: Electronic excitation energy transmission between pigment molecules

What's important to understand is that the travelling of the exciton to the reaction center does not involve the passing on of an electron. Instead, the excitation is transferred as electronic excitation energy through the antenna system until it reaches the reaction center where charge separation occurs. This process is also called excitation energy transfer, EET, and the moving excitation is referred to as an exciton. Depending on the strength of coupling between pigment molecules via intermolec-

ular forces, the exciton can also be delocalized over several pigments. (Mirkovic et al., 2017).

2.3.1 Förster-type transfer in the weak-coupling limit

When the pigments are far apart enough (but not too much) and there is weak electronic interactions between them compared to their interactions with the environment, EET usually happens via Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET). Hereby, the exciton transfer happens mainly via dipole-dipole interaction between the donor and acceptor pigment where the donor goes from excited to ground state and the acceptor from ground state to excited state. (Mirkovic et al., 2017)

When a pigment molecule is 'excited', one of its electrons is moved to a higher-energy orbital. The electron cloud is rearranged and this creates an oscillating electric dipole within the molecule. Therefore, the pigment molecule induces a dipole in its neighbour, thus transferring the electronic excitation energy, especially if the two pigments were previously interacting with intermolecular forces (ie. dipole-dipole forces).

The rate of Förster transfer depends on:

- Distance between donor and acceptor pigments (strongly distance-dependent, being indirectly proportional to R^6)
- Relative orientation of pigment molecules, referred to as orientation factor κ^2
- Spectral overlap between donor emission and acceptor absorption
- Environment (electrical and energetic)
- Donor excited-state lifetime and quantum yield (how effectively it can give off its exciton and how well it does that) (Mirkovic et al., 2017).

The 'emission' and 'absorption' spectra in donor and acceptor pigments refer to the wavelength of photon that the pigment *would* emit if it relaxed via fluorescence and the wavelength another pigment *would* be able to absorb.

2.3.2 Delocalised EET

Generalised Förster or Redfield approaches are used when pigments are close to each other and their electronic states mix. This produces exciton delocalisation over a cluster of pigment molecules. This facilitates the transfer of the exciton.

2.3.3 The role of the environment

The 'protein scaffold' (ie. the environment of the pigment molecules within the antenna) play an important part in the transfer of excitons. The proteins fix pigments in place and orientation through non-covalent interactions (intermolecular forces like hydrophobic packing, hydrogen bonding, or other interactions with the Mg_2^+ ion in the chlorophyll molecule). They partly determine

- energy levels (small shifts in excited-state energies due to local electric environment)
- electronic couplings between pigment molecules (by changing distance and orientation of individual pigments)
- vibrating interactions

(Croce & van Amerongen, 2020)

2.4 Step 3: Arriving at the center: 'The special pair'

In the reaction center (RC), there is a 'special pair' of chlorophyll molecules. In PSII, this is P680 and in PSI, it is P700. P680 consists of two chlorophyll molecules, often referred to as P_{D1} and P_{D2} or ChlD1 and ChlD2 because of the protein cores the chlorophylls bind to within (D1 and D2 also known as PsbA and PsbD). The name P680 comes from the fact that it has an absorption maximum at a wavelength of 680nm. Once excited, the special pair of chlorophyll (now referred to as P680*) doesn't return to its ground state through EET, but rather by giving off an electron through a redox reaction. This process is also called the charge separation. It is

rather similar in both P680 and P700 (ie. in PSII and PSI), with slightly different donor and acceptor proteins involved. (Shevela & Eaton-Rye, 2021; Cardona, Sedoud, Cox, & Rutherford, 2012)

2.5 Step 4: electron transfer chain in PSII on acceptor side

Before exploring the chemical reactions on the acceptor side of P680, it is useful to understand the oxidation and reduction states of quinones, as Q_A and Q_B are oxidised and reduced in this process.

- Q: oxidised quinone (two carbonyls, no electrons)
- $Q \cdot -$: Semiquinone radical (one electron added)
- QH_2 : Fully reduced quinol (two electrons and two protons added, carbonyls become hydroxyls)

(Gunner, 2009)

As previously explained, the reaction center is split up into two main parts, the D1 and D2 protein branch (named after the proteins). The D1 branch is the one participating in the Z-scheme, while the D2 remains mostly inactive.

Structurally, the P680, ChlD1, pheophytin (a chlorophyll like protein lacking the Mg_2^+ ion.) and Q_A form a fixed chain with fixed orientation to allow incredibly fast transmission of the electron. At the end of the chain, Q_B acts as the final receptor, it is however not tightly bound to the entire chain. ChlD2 is attached to P680 on the other branch with a slightly higher energy while ChlD1 makes the D1 branch slightly lower in energy. This encourages the electron transfer to take place along the D1 branch. It is not entirely known what function the D2 branch serves, but under normal conditions only the D1 branch is photochemically active.

Before being taken up by pheophytin, the electron moves to the accessory chlorophyll ChlD1 via a shift in electron density. This step is to lower the barrier for full charge separation. Another advantage is the spatial proximity that ChlD1 offers, making the forward transfer faster than recombination, improving the processes'

efficiency. ChlD1 having a lower energy state than ChlD2 favours the reaction along the D1 branch.

Still, the first redox reaction is said to be the oxidation of P680* and the reduction of pheophytin:

Pheo \cdot - is unstable and must pass on its electron to the next in line, Q_A . Q_A is a fixed plastoquinone which does not take in protons and accepts only one electron. This step increases the spatial separation of the electron from P680, suppressing recombination while ensuring the electron moves down a smooth energetic gradient. (put a pin on P_{680}^+ , will be covered later when explaining the donor side)

$Q_A \cdot -$ holds the electron only temporarily, passing it on to Q_B . Q_B is not fixed in place and is a semiquinone, meaning it needs two electrons and two protons to fully complete its transition to plastoquinol (PQH2).

A second charge-separation event happens and delivers a second electron to $Q_B \cdot -$. Concurrently, two protons are taken up from the stroma (contributing to a proton gradient!) to complete the reaction of $Q_B \cdot -$ to PQH2

Plastoquinol (PQH2) is now released and diffuses across the thylakoid membrane, delivering electrons to cytochrome b_6f (*cytb₆f*)

(Whitmarsh & Govindjee, 2002; Shevela & Eaton-Rye, 2021; Sirohiwal, Neese, & Pantazis, 2023; Kato & Noguchi, 2015; Lambrev et al., 2014)

2.6 Step 5: electron transfer chain on donor side in PSII

2.6.1 Overview

In order to be able to repeat this process repeatedly, PSII must reduce the P_{680}^+ which is the byproduct of the reduction of pheophytin. For this to happen, electrons must be provided. These electrons come from the Manganese complex (Mn_4CaO_5) through the so-called S-state cycle. Manganese has oxidation states ranging from I to V. Once this process has been repeated four times, H_2O is split into O_2 , $4H^+$ and $4e^-$ to in turn reduce the Manganese complex.

2.6.2 Oxygen-evolving complex (OEC)

The OEC is the site where water is ultimately split to extract its electrons and release O_2 . It is physically attached on the luminal side of PSII and contains the Mn_4CaO_5 cluster to control proton and electron transfer. It should be noted, however, that water is a very poor electron donor with an oxidation potential of $H_2O/O_2 +0.82V$, which means oxidising water requires a very strong oxidant. Luckily enough, after charge separation occurs, P_{680}^+ is one of the strongest oxidants known in biology with an oxidation potential of $+1.2V$, enough to extract electrons from the OEC and drive water oxidation. (Mandal, Saito, & Ishikita, 2019; Shevela & Eaton-Rye, 2021)

It comes to mind that, stoichiometrically, splitting water is not a one-electron process. In fact, the reaction $2H_2O \longrightarrow O_2 + 4H^+ + 4e^-$ shows that four electrons are removed for each O_2 molecule formed. Therefore, PSII must do a sequential charge-separation to accumulate enough oxidising equivalents to make the O-O form and release O_2 . This is why the OEC is said to be a 'charge accumulator' (accumulating the charges produced by repeating the same process four times until it can oxidise H_2O) (Li, Nakajima, Nomura, Kawakami, & Shen, 2024)

2.6.3 S-state cycle

Immediately after charge separation, the extremely strong oxidant P_{680}^+ must be reduced to avoid recombination with the just-released electron and photodamage.

In PSII, this happens through TyrZ (tyrosine residue on D1 protein, also known as D1-Tyr161) which quickly provides an electron to P_{680}^+ . At the same time, a proton is released from TyrZ, which helps with kinetics and redox powers, but I will not cover this (proton-coupled electron transfer, PCET).

TyrZ then oxidises the OEC (and gets a proton) to be fully regenerated while also advancing the OEC by one step in the 'Kok cycle' ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1 \rightarrow S_2 \rightarrow S_3 \rightarrow S_4$), storing 'oxidising equivalents'. After the fourth step, the highly oxidised OEC reacts with water to form O_2 to be brought back to S_0 while also pumping four protons into the lumen (contributing to proton gradient)

(Klauss, Haumann, & Dau, 2012; Li et al., 2024)

The structure of the OEC and a graphical overview of the S-state cycle can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: **Oxygen-evolving complex and S-state cycle.**
Note. Reprinted from (Vogt et al., 2015).

2.7 Step 6: Cytochrome b_6f and the Q-cycle

The Q-cycle (first proposed by Peter Mitchell in 1975) explains how electrons coming from PSII are transferred toward PSI and how this transfer increases the proton gradient across the thylakoid membrane. Electrons 'leave' PSII in the form of plastoquinol (PQH_2). Because PQH_2 is a mobile, 2-electron / 2-proton carrier, it can be oxidised back to plastoquinone (PQ) to extract its electrons. This oxidation happens in the cytochrome b_6f complex, and the extracted electrons are then passed to plastocyanine (Pc), which will deliver them to PSI.

2.7.1 Core function of cytochrome b_6f

- oxidise plastoquinol (PQH_2) to plastoquinone (PQ)
- reduce plastocyanine (Pc), which then reduces P_{700}^+ in PSI
- contribute to the proton gradient by a Q-cycle mechanism

In the Q-cycle, each PQH_2 oxidation releases its two protons to the lumen (contributing to proton gradient). In addition, the cycle uses protons from the stroma (again, contributing to proton gradient) to re-reduce PQ at the stromal (n-side) site. When the cycle is run twice (two "half-cycles"), 2 PQH_2 molecules are oxidised at the luminal site, 2 Pc molecules are reduced, and 1 PQH_2 molecule is regenerated at the stromal site from PQ (via a semiquinone intermediate) which can undergo oxidation again.

2.7.2 Structure of $cytb_6f$

$cytb_6f$ is a dimeric complex in the thylakoid membrane. Each monomer contains subunits and cofactors that enable two separate electron pathways:

- Cytochrome b_6 (PetB): contains the Q_o/Q_p site on the lumen (p) side where PQH_2 is oxidised and protons are released. It also contains the b-type hemes (commonly referred to as heme b_p and heme b_n) that form the low-potential pathway.

- Cytochrome f (PetA): contains heme f and is the terminal electron donor to plastocyanine (Pc).
- Rieske iron-sulfur protein (PetC): contains the [2 Fe–2 S] cluster and is mobile. It accepts an electron from PQH₂ at the Q_o/Q_p site and then moves toward cytochrome f to donate that electron onward.
- Q_i/Q_n site (stromal side): this is the n-side quinone reduction site, where PQ is reduced back (via semiquinone) and ultimately protonated to PQH₂ when the cycle has run twice.
- Small stabilising subunits (PetG, PetL, PetM, PetN, etc.): tightly bound membrane proteins that stabilise the complex.

note: n-side = negative side = stroma

2.7.3 The Q-cycle (overview)

It is useful to describe the Q-cycle as two half-reactions (“two runs”). This process is called ‘electron bifurcation’ because the two electrons from one PQH₂ are split, where one electron goes into a high-potential chain that reduces Pc, and the other goes into a low-potential chain that regenerates PQH₂.

2.7.4 Half-cycle 1: oxidation of PQH₂ at Q_o/Q_p site and creation of semiquinone on the n-side

A PQH₂ (plastoquinol) binds at the Q_o/Q_p site (which is on the luminal side) and is oxidised. Its protons directly go into the thylakoid lumen (contributing to proton gradient) while one of the electrons goes to the Rieske [2 Fe–2 S] cluster, then to cytochrome f (heme f) where it finally reduces plastocyanine (Pc). The other electron goes the low-potential route toward the stromal Q_i/Q_n site. It is transferred through the b-type hemes (b_p and b_n) toward the quinone site (n-side) where it reduces plastoquinone (PQ) to a semiquinone PQ· – where it is stored until this process is repeated a second time when the semiquinone is reduced to plastoquinol by taking up an additional two protons from the stroma (further contributing to proton

gradient). Therefore, one plastoquinol is regenerated for every 2 used, meaning the entire process just costs a net of 1 plastoquinol. For this reason, this process is also known as the 'double barrelled shotgun'.

The movement of the electron also generates an electric field, crucial to the proton motive force utilised by ATP synthase to generate ATP. For every pair of electrons coming into $\text{cyt}b_6f$, the difference in protons from lumen to stroma is increased by 6.

The structure of b_6f as well as the two different reaction paths with their corresponding redox potentials can be seen in Figure 5.

(Degen & Johnson, 2024; Malone, Proctor, Hitchcock, Hunter, & Johnson, 2021)

Figure 5: The proton motive Q-cycle of cytochrome b_6 .
Note. Reprinted from (Malone et al., 2021)

2.8 Step 7: Plastocyanine and delivery to PSI

Plastocyanin (Pc) is a small, soluble luminal electron carrier that transfers electrons from cytochrome b_6f (via cytochrome f) to the already-oxidised PSI (P700⁺), linking the two photosystems in linear electron flow. (Höhner et al., 2020; Wu, Hu, & Liu, 2025)

2.8.1 Pc with its Copper

Pc contains a single copper ion at its active site that cycles between the oxidised Cu(II) state and the reduced Cu(I) state during electron transfer. In chloroplasts, Pc has a relatively strong oxidation potential (commonly around 0.3V), making it possible for it to donate electrons to P₇₀₀⁺ while still being reducible by cytochrome f . (Mammoser & Happe, 2023; Wu et al., 2025)

2.8.2 Reduction of Pc by cytochrome b_6f

In cytochrome b_6f , electrons are passed on from PQH₂ to Pc. Chemically, this can be written by noting the copper oxidation state:

2.8.3 Diffusion through the thylakoid lumen

After reduction, Cu⁺Pc must physically travel through the aqueous thylakoid lumen to reach PSI.

(Höhner et al., 2020; Kirchhoff, 2004)

2.8.4 Luminal docking to PSI

PSI is considered a plastocyanine:ferredoxin reductase and has a lumen-facing binding region that positions Pc near P700 for efficient electron donation. PSI has a dedicated docking site for plastocyanine on its lumen-facing side, formed primarily by subunits PsaA and PsaB. Once the PsaA-PsaB/Pc complex forms, water

molecules cannot bind to the complex anymore due to strong hydrophobic interactions. Once Pc has been oxidised, a spatial rearrangement allows for water molecules to enter the complex and enhance dissociation.

(Caspary, Schwartz, Bayro-Kaiser, Fadeeva, & Nelson, 2021)

2.9 Step 8: PSI and the reduction of ferredoxin

The goal of PSI is to transfer an electron from Pc to ferredoxin (Fd), which will then be used to power reactions such as NADPH formation thanks to its strong reducing power.

2.9.1 Structure of PSI

PSI consists of several subunits, namely PsaA, PsaB, PsaC, PsaD and PsaE. Additionally, it has an antenna system used to absorb light energy and a chain of chlorophyll molecules used to transport the exciton to P700. Smaller membrane subunits (PsaF, PsaI, PsaJ, PsaK, PsaL and PsaM) stabilise the antenna system and ensure the quaternary shape of PSI is good.

2.9.2 Light absorption

The light absorption mechanism works similarly to the one in PSII where the exciton is transferred to P700 instead of P680

2.9.3 Electron transfer chain on acceptor side

When P700 absorbs excitation energy, it forms the excited state P_{700}^* . In this state, PSI becomes an extremely strong reductant (often cited around -1.2V), enabling electron donation to the first acceptor in the chain. (Webber & Lubitz, 2001; Brettel, 2001)

A simplified first charge-separation step is:

where A_0 is the primary electron acceptor

(Fromme, 2001; Lakshmi et al., 1999)

A_0 is a chlorophyll a-type molecule next to P700 ready for super-fast electron transfer.

A_1 is a phylloquinone as secondary electron acceptor which takes the electron from A_0^- and passes it to the iron-sulfur clusters.

Other cofactors

- F_X a [4 Fe-4 S] cluster in the PsaA/PsaB core
- F_A and F_B clusters bound by PsaC on the stromal side

Next, A_1^- reduces F_X , which is the first cluster. Then, F_X reduces F_A which in turn reduces F_B .

(Fromme, Jordan, & Krauß, 2003)

Ferredoxin (Fd) is a [2Fe-2S] soluble stromal acceptor protein carrying only one electron at a time. In iron-deficient organisms, flavodoxin is used instead.

(Brettel, 2001)

2.10 Step 9: Ferredoxin-NADP⁺ reductase (FNR)

The enzyme ferredoxin-NADP⁺ reductase (FNR) oxidises Fd(red) (coming from PSI) and produces NADPH.

2.10.1 Structure and binding

FNR is a V-shaped enzyme consisting of two domains: an FAD-binding domain and an NADP⁺-binding domain. The surface of the enzyme is complementary to that of ferredoxin (Fd) shape-wise, and positive residues on FNR allow for even more efficient binding of Fd(red).

2.10.2 Overall reaction

The general reaction equation for the oxidation of ferredoxin and reduction of NADP⁺ is:

2.10.3 Why an FAD intermediate is needed

Fd is a single-electron donor while NADP^+ is a two-electron acceptor. To overcome this difference, the flavoenzyme cofactor FAD is used as a temporary electron carrier within FNR.

2.10.4 Stepwise redox sequence at FNR (FAD states and naming)

As reduced ferredoxin binds to FNR, it donates one electron to FAD. This creates an anionic radical semiquinone state, and FNR is then referred to as FNRsq.

This anionic radical is protonated to become $\text{FADH}\cdot$. $\text{FADH}\cdot$ is then reduced by another reduced ferredoxin molecule, becoming FADH^- . In this state, FNR is referred to as FNRred. Another proton is taken up:

Finally, FADH_2 reduces NADP^+ (and releases a proton into the lumen, contributing to proton gradient):

which produces NADPH, crucial for the dark phase of photosynthesis and thus the generation of carbohydrates.

2.10.5 Proton source

Note: the protons taken up come from the stromal water (contributing to proton gradient).

(Bruns & Karplus, 1995; Kean, Kuo, & Karplus, 2018; Cassan, Lagoutte, & Sétif, 2005)

2.11 Intermezzo: Cyclic electron transfer

The processes of cyclic electron transfer remains not well understood. Only recently have researchers been able to start understanding the reactions taking place in cyclic electron transfer.

Cyclic electron transfer shifts the balance between NADPH / ATP by producing less NADPH and contributing to proton gradient, yielding more ATP. Electrons do not go to the FNR (unlike during linear electron flow) in cyclic electron flow.

There are two pathways for cyclic electron transfer (also known as CET or CEF), the primary PGR5 pathway and the secondary NDH route. Both have no net effect on oxidation states (which is why they're cycles). Both of these proteins are elusive and the exact mechanisms of electron transfer, including individual transporters active in CET, are still unknown.

The PGR5 (proton gradient regulation) route is one mechanism which has been proposed to regulate CET. PGR5 is a small, stroma-soluble protein which is bound to thylakoids by PGRL1. PGRL1 could be the mysterious FQR molecule which directly reduces quinones in CET, however experiments by Nawrocki et. al. have shown that both PGR5 and PGRL1 only play indirect roles in CET. In broad terms, PGR5 is thought to be reduced by Fd(red) and then in turn reduce PQ from the quinone pool to PQH2 with the necessary protons for this reaction being supplied by the stroma.

The NDH (NAD(P)H dehydrogenase) route is thought to be critical at high levels of light, where regular PGR5 pumps too many protons to the lumen and nonphotochemical fluorescence quenching (NPQ) takes place, which in turn slows down electron transfer in *cytb₆f*. It also provides a more proton-efficient route, though again the exact mechanisms and its actual relevance are still not well understood. In broad terms, two Fd(red) proteins reduce NDH (which can store electrons transiently), which can then, coupled with two protons from the stroma, reduce PQ to PQH2.

In both cases, the plastoquinone (PQH2) then goes through the cytochrome *b₆f* complex again (pumping protons into the lumen, which is the goal of CET) and

producing Pc, which then gives the electron back to PSI, completing the cycle.

When is it triggered?

Again this is a bit unclear, but the CET is thought to be conditionally activated at low NADP⁺ levels or high Fd(red) levels or a relatively high demand in ATP (compared to NADPH demand)

(Nawrocki et al., 2019; Yamamoto & Shikanai, 2018; G. N. Johnson, 2011; Degen, 2023)

2.12 Step 10: ATP synthesis

ATP synthase uses the proton gradient generated during the light phase of photosynthesis to synthesise ATP from ADP and inorganic phosphate, PO₄³⁻.

2.12.1 Structure

Chloroplast ATP synthase consists of the CF1 and CF0 subunits as well as the peripheral stalk. The peripheral stalk is made up of delta, b and b' subunits and holds CF1 in a non-rotary state. CF1 is soluble in the stroma, while CF0 is hydrophobic, which is why it is embedded in the thylakoid membrane. The structure of ATP synthase can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: **ATP synthase structure and proton-driven rotation.**
Note. Reprinted from (Tamang, 2023).

2.12.2 CF1: catalytic head (where ATP is formed)

CF1 consists of 3 alpha subunits and 3 catalytic beta subunits, forming a hexamer. ADP diffuses into active sites of the beta subunits and is held in place by hydrogen bonds. An Mg^{2+} ion neutralises the ADP and provides extra stability. Inorganic phosphate also enters the active site, and ATP is formed. The conformational shifts coming from the rotation of the CF1 unit facilitate the binding of ADP and inorganic phosphate.

2.12.3 CF0: membrane motor (how the proton gradient drives rotation)

CF0 consists of a c-subunit ring which rotates, as well as an a-subunit which is not well understood. The a-subunit includes an access channel for protons from the thylakoid lumen. A proton is carried for almost a full rotation in the form of a protonated glutamate on the c-ring, until it can leave via an exit channel leading to the high-pH chloroplast stroma, which deprotonates the glutamate. The central rotor is made up of the c-ring, gamma and epsilon subunit.

2.12.4 Stoichiometry

ATP synthase is thought to produce one ATP per 4.67 H^+ molecules pumped through the ATP synthase.

(He, Miginiac-Maslow, Sigalat, Keryer, & Haraux, 2000; Hahn, Vonck, Mills, Meier, & Kühlbrandt, 2020)

3 Dark reactions: Carbon fixation

The dark reactions of photosynthesis are typically categorised as C3, C4 or CAM reactions, depending on the pathway (or more specifically, the carbon-concentrating mechanism) they use. A graphical overview of all three pathways can be seen under Figure 7.

Figure 7: C3, C4 and CAM carbon fixation strategies.
Note. Reprinted from (GeeksforGeeks, 2025).

3.1 Calvin-Benson Cycle (C3)

3.1.1 Overview

The light phase of photosynthesis generates ATP to power endergonic reactions and NADPH as a reducing agent. In the Calvin-Benson cycle (CBC), these two substances are used to capture CO₂ and convert it into substances that will be used for the production of carbohydrates. (Blankenship, 2021; M. P. Johnson, 2024)

Our understanding of carbon fixation was greatly advanced by Calvin, Benson and Bassham, who used two-dimensional chromatography and ¹⁴C radioactive isotope tracking to map the pathway. (Encyclopedia of the Environment, n.d.; Blankenship, 2021)

Note: side products of the detailed chemical reactions below, such as HOPO_4^{2-} ions, H^+ ions, or ADP, will not be explicitly mentioned each time. I will also keep track of the number of carbons in specific molecules (eg. 5C, for 5-carbon molecules) for better understanding.

3.1.2 Carboxylation

Reaction sequence (carbon fixation)

(1) RuBP (5C) is converted into an enediolate intermediate (double bond with two O⁻ groups, highly reactive, making addition of CO₂ possible) reacts with CO₂ in the RuBisCo active site (enzyme) to form an unstable 6-carbon intermediate (2-carboxy-3-ketoarabinitol-1,5-bisphosphate). This intermediate is rapidly hydrolysed and splits into two molecules of 3-phosphoglycerate (PGA, 3C). (Blankenship, 2021; Kent, 2000)

Structure of RuBisCo

RuBisCo consists of 8 large subunits and 8 small subunits. Although the carboxylation reaction is highly exergonic, it is still rather slow in kinetic terms.

The active site contains a critical lysine residue that binds a non-substrate (ie. doesn't take part in reaction) CO₂ molecule to form a carbamate ion, which then binds Mg²⁺. The Mg²⁺ ion is critical for catalytic function and enhances the effectiveness with which RuBP and CO₂ react.

3.1.3 Reduction

In the reduction phase, the 3-carbon product of carboxylation (PGA) is converted into the triose phosphate glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate (GAP, also called G3P). This requires ATP and NADPH (to reduce it). The outcome is that carbon is now in a reduced, energy-rich form that can either exit the cycle to contribute to carbohydrate synthesis or remain in the cycle for RuBP regeneration (5 of 6 carbon dioxide molecules will be 'used' to regenerate RuBP, while only one contributes to actual carbohydrate synthesis). (Blankenship, 2021; M. P. Johnson, 2024)

Reaction sequence (PGA to GAP)

(2) PGA is phosphorylated by ATP using 3-phosphoglycerate kinase to form 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate (BPG, 3C), also making ADP.

(3) BPG is reduced by NADPH (and protonated) using NADP-glyceraldehyde phosphate dehydrogenase to form glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate (GAP, 3C also known as G3P), releasing NADP^+ and inorganic phosphate (Pi).

For every 3 molecules of CO_2 , 6 molecules of GAP are produced. Only one of these is used to make carbohydrates, while the remaining five are used to regenerate RuBP in a series of reactions that also require ATP. (as already stated earlier)

3.1.4 Regeneration of RuBP

Reaction sequence (carbon rearrangements to reform RuBP)

(4) One GAP is converted to dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP, 3C) using triose phosphate isomerase.

(5) DHAP (3C) combines with GAP (3C) using aldolase to produce fructose-1,6-bisphosphate (FBP, 6C).

(6) FBP is dephosphorylated by fructose-1,6-bisphosphate phosphatase to fructose-6-phosphate (F6P, 6C), releasing inorganic phosphate.

(7) F6P reacts with another GAP (3C) using transketolase, producing erythrose-4-phosphate (E4P, 4C) and xylulose-5-phosphate (X5P, 5C).

(8) Another DHAP (3C) reacts with E4P (4C) using aldolase to form sedoheptulose-1,7-bisphosphate (SBP, 7C).

(9) SBP is dephosphorylated using sedoheptulose-1,7-bisphosphate phosphatase to sedoheptulose-7-phosphate (S7P, 7C), releasing inorganic phosphate.

(10) S7P (7C) and GAP (3C) react using transketolase to form ribose-5-phosphate (R5P, 5C) and xylulose-5-phosphate (X5P, 5C).

(11) X5P and R5P are converted to ribulose-5-phosphate (Ru5P, 5C) using ribulose-5-phosphate epimerase and ribulose-5-phosphate isomerase, respectively.

(12) Ru5P is phosphorylated with ATP using phosphoribulokinase to regenerate RuBP and ADP.

These reactions ensure that the organism doesn't run out of RuBP to fix CO₂ molecules. Figure 8 and Figure 9 provide a graphical overview of the reactions reducing CO₂, regenerating RuBP and the synthesis of carbohydrates.

Reduction of CO_2

- ① $\text{RuBP (5C)} + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{6C enediolate intermediate}$
 $\rightarrow 2\text{PGA (3C)}$
- ② $\text{PGA} + \text{ATP} \rightarrow \text{BPg (3C)} + \text{ADP}$
- ③ $\text{BPg} + \text{NADPH} \rightarrow \text{GAP (3C, aka. G3P)} + \text{NADP}^+ + \text{P}_i$

Regeneration of RuBP

- ④ $\text{GAP} \xrightarrow{\text{triose phosphate isomerase}} \text{DHAP (3C)}$
- ⑤ $\text{DHAP} + \text{GAP} \rightarrow \text{FBP (6C)}$
- ⑥ $\text{FBP} \rightarrow \text{F6P (6C)} + \text{P}_i$
- ⑦ $\text{F6P} + \text{GAP} \rightarrow \text{E4P (4C)} + \text{X5P (5C)}$
- ⑧ $\text{DHAP} + \text{E4P} \rightarrow \text{SBP (7C)}$
- ⑨ $\text{SBP} \rightarrow \text{S7P (7C)} + \text{P}_i$
- ⑩ $\text{S7P} + \text{GAP} \rightarrow \text{R5P (5C)} + \text{X5P (5C)}$
- ⑪ a) $\text{X5P} \rightarrow \text{Ru5P}$
b) $\text{R5P} \rightarrow \text{Ru5P}$
- ⑫ $\text{Ru5P} + \text{ATP} \rightarrow \text{RuBP} + \text{ADP}$

Transformation

Glucose

- ⑬ $\text{F6P} + \text{UDP-glucose} \rightarrow \text{S6P} + \text{UDP}$
- ⑭ $\text{S6P} \rightarrow \text{Sucrose} + \text{P}_i$

Starch

- ⑮ $\text{G1P} + \text{ATP} \rightarrow \text{ADP-glucose} + \text{P}_i$
- ⑯ $\text{Glucan}_n + \text{ADP-glucose} \rightarrow \text{Glucan}_{n+1} + \text{ADP}$

Key substances

Figure 8: **Calvin-Benson cycle overview (1/2)**
Note. Created by the author.

G1P : glucose where carbon 1 has a phosphate ;
can be converted to nucleotide sugars like
ADP-glc. or UDP-glc.

ADP-glc. : "activated glucose" : nucleotide sugar
used in starch synthesis

PPi : pyrophosphate : $P_2O_7^{4-}$

Glucan : polymer made of glucose units

UDP : uridine diphosphate (+ 2 phosphates) ; usually
built after ...

UDP-glc. : activated nucleotide sugar

3.1.5 Stoichiometry

The synthesis of one mol of GAP requires 9 mol of ATP and 6 mol of NADPH, giving a ratio of 1.5 ATP/NADPH. Linear electron transfer yields only 1.28 ATP/NADPH (assuming an ATP synthase ratio of $4.67 \text{ H}^+/\text{ATP}$). The missing ATP is thought to be produced by cyclic electron transfer. (M. P. Johnson, 2024; Blankenship, 2021)

This pathway (which I just explained) is called C3 because its key exported product is GAP, a 3-carbon sugar.

3.1.6 The competing reaction: Oxygenation (photorespiration)

RuBisCo can catalyse a competing reaction where it binds O_2 instead of CO_2 . This produces less useful carbon output (obviously) and forces the plant to spend additional ATP, reducing overall photosynthetic efficiency. (Blankenship, 2021; Kent, 2000)

Instead of producing two PGA molecules, oxygenation produces one PGA molecule and one phosphoglycolate (2C). Phosphoglycolate is processed through a series of reactions that regenerate PGA and release CO_2 , but these steps require additional ATP, leading to energy loss.

Even though carboxylation is more favourable, the substantially higher concentration of O_2 compared to CO_2 leads to a typical ratio of about 3:1 to 4:1 for carboxylation:oxygenation.

Plants counteract the comparatively low efficiency of RuBisCo by producing large amounts of it, which is why RuBisCo can make up 30–50% of total soluble protein mass in spinach, for example. (Andersson, 1996)

3.2 C4 pathway

Because RuBisCo's oxygenation side reaction becomes less problematic at higher CO_2 concentrations, concentrating CO_2 around RuBisCo increases carbon fixation efficiency. C4 plants achieve this through spatial separation of initial CO_2 capture and the Calvin cycle using Kranz anatomy.

C4 plants have a bundle sheath of cells surrounding a central vein, and these

bundle sheath cells are surrounded by mesophyll cells. Mesophyll cells contain high concentrations of phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) carboxylase, which does not bind O_2 . PEP carboxylase fixes CO_2 into oxaloacetate (4C), which is reduced by NADPH to malate (a 4C acid), which is where the C4 name comes from.

Malate is transported from the mesophyll cells to the bundle sheath cells, where it is decarboxylated to form pyruvate and regenerate NADPH and CO_2 . The released CO_2 is then taken up by RuBisCo in the Calvin cycle. Pyruvate is transported back to the mesophyll cells and converted back to PEP through again phosphorylation by ATP. (Dai, Ku, & Edwards, 1993; Blankenship, 2021)

This also allows C4 plants to continue photosynthesising with stomata more closed, reducing water loss and improving performance in warmer climates (because they have some CO_2 stored and they can use it over a longer period of time before having to take up atmospheric air again.

(Dai et al., 1993; Kent, 2000; Blankenship, 2021)

3.3 CAM pathway

Crassulacean acid metabolism (CAM) is another CO_2 concentration strategy, working best in very hot environments (for example deserts, where cacti use it). CAM plants separate CO_2 capture and the Calvin cycle in time rather than space.

CAM plants open their stomata mainly at night, conserving water. During the night they fix CO_2 to malate similarly to C4 plants. Malate is stored, and during the day the stomata close again; malate is then decarboxylated and the released CO_2 enters the Calvin cycle.

CAM plants conserve water extremely well but have lower photosynthetic efficiency, which is why they cannot compete with C3 or C4 plants when water is not scarce.

(Kent, 2000; Encyclopedia of the Environment, n.d.; Blankenship, 2021; M. P. Johnson, 2024; Dai et al., 1993)

3.4 GAP to carbohydrates (sucrose and starch)

3.4.1 Overview: linking GAP production to end-product synthesis

The Calvin–Benson cycle produces triose phosphates (GAP and its isomer DHAP) in the chloroplast stroma. These triose phosphates are either exported to the cytosol for sucrose synthesis (export form of carbohydrate), or retained in the chloroplast and converted into starch (for temporary storage). (Fischer, 2011; Hilgers et al., 2018)

Sucrose is typically synthesised during the day for immediate use, while starch accumulates in the chloroplast during the day and is used at night to for the metabolism and sucrose supply when photosynthesis stops. (Geigenberger & Stitt, 2000; Martins et al., 2013)

3.4.2 Export

The triose-phosphate/phosphate translocator (TPT) helps exchange triose phosphates with inorganic phosphate across the chloroplast inner envelope. (Fischer, 2011)

3.4.3 Sucrose synthesis (cytosol)

Sucrose is synthesised in the cytosol via two reactions: sucrose-phosphate synthase (SPS) forms sucrose-6-phosphate (Suc₆P) from fructose-6-phosphate (F₆P) and UDP-glucose, and sucrose-phosphate phosphatase (SPP) hydrolyses Suc₆P to sucrose.

(13) SPS: formation of sucrose-6-phosphate

(14) SPP: dephosphorylation to sucrose

(Albi & Serrato, 2016)

3.4.4 Starch synthesis (chloroplast stroma)

Starch synthesis uses ADP-glucose as the glucosyl donor. The first step is the production of ADP-glucose from glucose-1-phosphate (G1P) and ATP, catalysed by ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase (AGPase).

(15) AGPase: activation of glucose for polymerisation

(16) Starch synthases (SS): chain elongation using ADP-glucose

(Pfister & Zeeman, 2016; Ballicora, Iglesias, & Preiss, 2004)

3.4.5 Regulation

At low photosynthesis levels, mostly sucrose is produced. When the rate of photosynthesis increases, more starch is built up. Regulation of SPS therefore controls the ratio of starch to sucrose present in the plant. SPS activity is regulated through phosphorylation of its active sites, by SPS phosphatase.

3.4.6 Avoiding unnecessary cycling: FBPase

Another important enzyme is FBPase, which prevents an unnecessary cycle where F6P is phosphorylated to F1,6BP via phosphofructokinase and then dephosphorylated back to F6P by FBPase, wasting energy. To avoid this, FBPase redirects carbon toward formation of hexose phosphates. (Cassan et al., 2005)

4 Biological sites of photosynthesis

In plants and algae, oxygenic photosynthesis happens in chloroplasts, which came about from endosymbiotic cyanobacteria and therefore still have an internal membrane. (Blankenship, 2010; Jensen & Leister, 2014)

The chloroplast is enclosed by a double membrane envelope (outer and inner membrane) that separates the chloroplast from the cytosol and controls exchange and of substances. The aqueous stroma (interior), contains the enzymes of the Calvin-Benson cycle, which is why carbon fixation and the production of triose phosphates (GAP/DHAP) occur in the stroma. (Jensen & Leister, 2014; Blankenship, 2021)

The light-dependent reactions occur in the thylakoid membrane, which is divided into stacked grana and unstacked stroma lamellae (intergranal thylakoids). Photosystem II and the oxygen-evolving complex are present in grana thylakoids, while Photosystem I and ATP synthase are mainly found in the stroma-facing thylakoids, enabling an efficient connection of electron transfer and ATP synthesis. The thylakoid lumen (the aqueous space inside thylakoids) acts as the main proton pool, while the stroma remains the proton-poor side, building up the proton motive force used by ATP synthase. (Jensen & Leister, 2014; Blankenship, 2021)

Finally, the site of carbohydrate synthesis depends on export from the chloroplast: triose phosphates produced in the stroma can either be retained for starch synthesis in the chloroplast, or exported to the cytosol via the triose-phosphate/phosphate translocator (TPT) for sucrose synthesis. (Jensen & Leister, 2014; Blankenship, 2021)

Figure 10 provides a graphical simplification of the chloroplast.

Chloroplast

Figure 10: **Graphical simplification of the chloroplast**(Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc., 2026)

5 Artificial photosynthesis

5.1 Going artificial

The incredible mechanisms underlying photosynthesis detailed above have shown how seemingly simple systems have evolved to great complexity to capture light energy in the most efficient way possible. Motivated by an energy crisis and climate change as well as academic research purposes, scientists have started to try to build photosynthetic systems themselves.

5.2 Introduction

At its core, artificial photosynthesis aims to harness light energy and convert carbon dioxide and water into energy-rich chemicals, storing solar energy in chemical bonds. The means by which this is achieved can vary, however the core functions are heavily inspired by natural photosynthesis. The degree to which it resembles natural photosynthesis can vary between methods. Oftentimes, chemical products include methane, ethanol or H_2 , as they are more useful to us humans in an industrial setting than sucrose or glucose, for example.

5.3 Definition and scope

In this section, I will not go in-depth on any setup qualified as 'artificial photosynthesis', as this would exceed the scope of my project. Additionally, the field of artificial photosynthesis is fairly new and many methods employed are not made publicly available as they have been designed by companies aiming to industrialise their projects. I will therefore focus on exploring the different types of setups for artificial photosynthesis, highlight their differences and provide a rough understanding of their workings while building upon the chemical mechanisms explored in the section on natural photosynthesis.

The fundamental functions an artificial photosynthetic system must be able to accomplish are:

- light absorption and excitation,

- charge separation,
- spatial separation of oxidation and reduction reactions,
- catalytic multi-electron chemistry.

(Fujishima & Honda, 1972; Lewis & Nocera, 2006)

5.4 Classification of artificial photosynthetic approaches

Artificial photosynthetic systems can be classified according to how light energy is converted into chemical potential. I distinguish between the following four approaches:

- photochemical systems
- photovoltaic-driven electrochemical systems (biophotovoltaics)
- biohybrid systems

This classification shows the difference in spatial and functional separation between light harvesting, charge transport, and catalysis employed.

5.5 Photochemical artificial photosynthesis

5.5.1 Logic & definition

Photochemical systems use molecular or other inorganic light absorbers that directly use photon energy to generate excited electronic states to drive redox reactions.

Upon light absorption, a photosensitiser (PS) is promoted to an excited state:

The excited state can either donate or accept an electron, giving it a different charge which subsequently drives redox reactions.

5.5.2 Engineering setup

Typical photochemical systems consist of:

- a molecular photosensitiser (e.g. Ru-, Ir-, or organic dye complexes)
- a sacrificial electron donor or acceptor
- a catalyst for fuel formation

5.5.3 Chemical reactions

Here is an example of a setup that would use light energy to produce H₂, which could be used directly as hydrogen fuel

D stands for a sacrificial donor. Unfortunately, many photochemical systems are not energetically closed and require consumable reagents, which strongly inhibits their usability. (Ferreira, Iverson, Maghlaoui, Barber, & Iwata, 2008; Kärkäs, Verho, Johnston, & Åkermark, 2014)

5.6 Biophotovoltaics

5.6.1 Logic and definition

Cyanobacterial biophotovoltaic (BPV) systems intervene in the electron transport chain of oxygenic organisms to generate electrical current. Instead of directing light-derived electrons toward NADPH production and carbon fixation, a fraction of these electrons is diverted to an external electrode, to produce electricity.

This can therefore be seen as the 'opposite' of other artificial photosynthesis techniques, which use artificial ways of harnessing light energy and store the electrical energy as chemical energy using biological approaches.

5.6.2 Origin of electrons from H₂O

The ultimate electron source is water. Charge separation at Photosystem II (PSII) generates P680⁺, which extracts electrons from water via the oxygen-evolving complex (OEC). These electrons must now somehow be intercepted.

5.6.3 Intracellular electron transport and leakage points

Electron extraction does not occur directly at PSII, as the OEC and primary acceptors are part of its structure and it would be very difficult to intercept them here. Instead, electrons are harvested from redox pools of already-reduced biological substances.

Plastoquinone pool Reduced plastoquinone (PQH₂) is a soluble, two-electron carrier. Under certain conditions, electrons from the PQ pool can be transferred to introduced substances to 'steal' electrons.

Photosystem I and ferredoxin Electrons exiting PSI reduce ferredoxin (Fd). Reduced ferredoxin can donate electrons to alternative substances, including artificial mediators.

5.6.4 Mediator-based electron transfer

Soluble redox mediators can bring electrons from the cell to the anode. Examples include:

- endogenous (e.g. quinones, phenazines) mediators (already native to cells)
- exogenous (e.g. ferricyanide, viologens) mediators (artificially introduced to cell)

(McCormick et al., 2011; Bombelli et al., 2011)

5.7 Biohybrid and semi-artificial photosynthesis

5.7.1 Logic and definition

Biohybrid photosynthesis uses semiconductors or dyes to harvest light and supplies electrons to enzymes or microbes that can do selective chemistry like H₂ production or CO₂ fixation. This can be made by building enzyme-electrode systems or surrounding microbes with photoactive materials. (Fang, Kalathil, & Reisner, 2020; Brown, Wilker, Boehm, Dukovic, & King, 2012)

5.7.2 Mechanism

Step 1: semiconductor photoexcitation

A semiconductor creates an electron-hole pair when a photon hits it. The conduction-band electrons can then reduce biological catalysts while the holes must be filled by oxidising a donor (like water or an artificial donor)

Step 2: electron delivery

- direct contact: enzyme or cell interacts physically with the semiconductor
- redox mediators: soluble shuttle substances (similar to PQH₂, Pc or Fd)
- photoactive layers built directly on cell surfaces

Enzymes typically need very specific redox potential and fast delivery, which is what makes this technique of artificial photosynthesis so difficult.

Step 3: formation of products

A well-studied example is the combination of light-harvesting semiconductors to CO₂-fixing bacteria, where electrons provide reducing power and the cell provides a metabolic pathway to a target product. One demonstrated case is a semiconductor–bacteria biohybrid producing acetate from CO₂ via the Wood–Ljungdahl pathway (Gai, Cai, Li, & Chen, 2020; Kornienko, Zhang, Sakimoto, Yang, & Reisner, 2018)

Another implication can be the formation of formate from CO₂ directly with the help of formate dehydrogenase

(Fang et al., 2020; Armstrong & Hirst, 2011; Torella et al., 2015)

6 Genetic engineering and its applications in photosynthesis

6.1 Fundamentals of Genetic Engineering

6.1.1 Recombinant DNA techniques and gene editing

This section will focus on the CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing technique. Of course, there are other methods used as well, but this is the one most commonly used at the moment.

CRISPR-Cas9 is a bacterial immune system mechanism that aims to protect the bacterium from bacteriophages. The goal is that a Cas9 protein cuts the intruder's DNA and remembers a part of it for defence. This mechanism has been used in the field of gene editing.

Step 1: Adaptation: Acquiring a new spacer

The bacterial genome contains a CRISPR array, a region in the DNA made of alternating repeats (identical sequences of DNA) and spacers (variable sequences of DNA).

When a bacteriophage infects a bacterium, the proteins Cas1 and Cas2 identify a protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) in its genetic sequence. In the case of type II Cas9 genetic engineering (which is most commonly used in gene editing and is the method I will focus on) this PAM is a sequence of NGG (any nucleotide, guanine, guanine). Upstream of this PAM, Cas1-Cas2 take a fragment of that DNA (often called pre-spacer) and incorporate it in the bacterium's CRISPR array as a spacer, while also adding a repeat unit afterwards. The pre-spacer becomes a spacer in the bacterial genome.

Step 2: Expression: Making the guide RNAs (pre-crRNA, tracrRNA, RNase III)

The CRISPR array is then transcribed into pre-crRNA, containing spacers and repeats. tracrRNA is a separate genetic sequence from somewhere else in the genome. It contains a region that is complementary to the repeat sequence in the pre-crRNA and therefore base-pairs with them, forming a double-stranded RNA. Cas9 helps in

the formation, which is why it is called Cas9-dependent maturation pathway.

The enzyme RNase III cuts this segment, producing a crRNA (including spacer information and repeat parts) and tracrRNA. These two RNAs remain paired via base-pairing and form crRNA:tracrRNA, which fixes onto Cas9 as 'guide RNA'.

Step 3: Interference: Finding the target and cutting it

The Cas9 with its guide RNA looks for DNA with a PAM. In this case, the PAM is 5'-NGG-3' and precedes the target sequence (protospacer). Cas9 then opens the DNA and tests if its guide RNA matches bases with the examined DNA. If that is the case, the guide RNA connects with the DNA strand, forming an R-loop. Cas9 then changes shape and cuts the DNA a few base-pairs above the PAM, producing a double-strand break (DSB). This reaction requires Mg^{2+} to catalyse phosphodiester bond hydrolysis.

The bacterium's CRISPR array contains spacer sequences that match invader DNA, so in principle it could be targeted. A major protection mechanism is that the CRISPR locus does not present the correct PAM adjacent to the spacer-derived target sequences in the way invading DNA does. Without a correct PAM, Cas9 won't start the DNA opening and does also not proceed to cleavage.

(Douch, 2022; Sander & Joung, 2014; Bock, 2015)

6.1.2 Repair mechanisms

Non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) NHEJ is the cell's default repair mechanism, being faster but also more inaccurate. The break is recognised immediately by the Ku70/80 heterodimer, which binds the DNA ends within seconds and recruits other repair factors. These proteins process the damaged ends to make them chemically compatible for ligation, often requiring nucleases to trim incompatible overhangs and polymerases to fill holes. The final step, called 'ligation', is done by DNA ligase IV which directly rejoins the DNA backbone (no template required). Other key scaffold proteins are: DNA-PKcs, XRCC4, XLF (NHEJ1), PAXX, APLF (I didn't explain their specific role, as this section's objective is to give the reader an overview of genetic engineering methods)

This process frequently introduces small insertions or deletions (indels) at the

break site. This error-prone nature makes NHEJ ideal for gene knockouts, where the goal is to disrupt gene function rather than introduce specific sequences. The indels often shift the reading frame, producing a nonfunctional protein.

Homology-directed repair (HDR) This method uses a homologous DNA template to guide repair, allowing the introduction of specific mutations or entire gene sequences. The cell first processes the broken ends to expose single-stranded DNA, then uses a matching DNA template to copy the correct information and restore the broken region with high accuracy.

For genetic engineering, researchers supply an artificial donor template containing the desired genetic modification flanked by "homology arms" (sequences matching the DNA on either side of the break, making the cell think that this DNA sequence is the repair template for the broken DNA).

The usage of the artificial donor template over the actual sister chromatid is a stochastic process. Therefore, scientists make sure that enough artificial templates are present in the cell during HDR to ensure that this genetic sequences is incorporated in the cell's genome.

(Jasin & Rothstein, 2013; Symington, 2016; Douch, 2022)

Figure 11 shows a graphical simplification for both HDR and NHEJ repair mechanisms.

Figure 11: **HDR** vs **NHEJ** repair pathways.
Note. Reprinted from (InVivo Biosystems, 2024).

CRISPR as an immune response in bacteria

For immunal response in bacteria, CRISPR incorporates a viral DNA sequence in its array, which is then given to Cas9 for screening. As soon as Cas9 finds a DNA sequence containing the PAM and the complementary DNA sequence to its spacerRNA, it cuts it. Therefore, viral DNA cannot be spread within the bacterium as well, because Cas9 would always cut it.

6.1.3 Gene expression regulation and promoter systems

Gene regulation is how a cell controls which genes, out of the many genes in its genome, are "turned on" (expressed). Thanks to gene regulation, each cell type in your body has a different set of active genes – despite the fact that almost all the cells of your body contain the exact same DNA. These different patterns of gene expression cause your various cell types to have different sets of proteins, making each cell type uniquely specialized to do its job. " - (Khan Academy, n.d.)

Genes can be regulated at several layers. Important genes are sometimes regulated on multiple layers simultaneously.

Gene expression regulation

- Transcriptional control
 - Chromatin accessibility: structure of chromatin makes genes more or less available for transcription
 - Promoters and enhancers: Promoter is the region around the transcription start site; changing it changes how efficiently initiation happens. Enhancers increase the expression of a target gene.
 - Transcription factors: transcription factors bind to sequences on the DNA at a gene and promote or repress its transcription into RNA
- Post-transcriptional control
 - mRNA stability: stability of mRNA obviously has an effect on how much of it is translated

- RNA processing: splicing: removing introns of pre-mRNA, crucial step for translation. Sometimes adding an intron increases the expression of a gene. (yourgenome.org, n.d.)
- Translational control
- Post-translational control
 - Protein activity: proteins themselves can be tagged or modified, which can affect their activity and functionality

Instead of only changing genome, we can also change how this genome is expressed.

6.1.4 Chloroplast vs. nuclear genome transformation

Genetic engineering to improve photosynthesis can target either the chloroplast genome or the nuclear genome. Chloroplast transformation is technically limited to fewer species and specific properties, especially when they span the entire cell, depend on nuclear control. Nuclear engineering is more broadly used for crop gene editing and is essential for most photosynthesis-related targets because the majority of chloroplast proteins are actually nuclear-encoded (Bock, 2015; South, Cavanagh, Liu, & Ort, 2019)

6.2 Strategies for improving photosynthetic efficiency

Similarly to the section on artificial photosynthesis, I will not go into mechanistic depth here, but rather just explore different strategies and discuss their results.

6.2.1 RuBisCo optimisation

RuBisCo being a crucial enzyme in the Calvin-Benson cycle and also one of the slowest enzymes known to mankind, it is the first obvious target for improving photosynthesis. Multiple strategies have been investigated to enhance RuBisCo's activity, such as simply increasing its concentration, genetically improving its catalytic rate, improving its CO₂ specificity, increasing the concentration of the enzyme activating it or concentrating CO₂ (carbon concentrating mechanisms, CCM)

RuBisCo activase is the enzyme activating RuBisCo. It is extremely heat-sensitive, which is one of the reasons why carbon capture becomes more inefficient as temperature increases. Making RuBisCo activase more thermostable by introducing genes from heat-adapted species has shown to improve plant growth. Additionally, many plants overproduce RuBisCo in comparison to RuBisCo activase which leads to lower efficiency in photosynthesis. Genetically modified species that overproduce both RuBisCo and RuBisCo activase have shown to have higher CO₂ assimilation (Suganami, Suzuki, Sato, & Makino, 2021)

Many 'faster' RuBisCo's show decreased CO₂ affinity. Therefore, making it faster is only helpful by increasing CO₂ concentration by incorporating carbon-concentrating mechanisms. For example, Tobacco's native chloroplast *rbcL* was replaced with RuBisCo large and small subunit genes from *Halothiobacillus neapolitanus*. The mutants assembled functional L8S8 RuBisCo in their chloroplasts and had 2-fold faster carboxylation rate. However, they required elevated CO₂ concentrations (ca. 1%) to grow properly. Producing fast and active Rubisco in tobacco to enhance photosynthesis. (Chen & Whitney, 2023)

6.2.2 Broader light absorption spectrum

Broadening the light absorption spectrum can be achieved through different methods. One opportunity is exploiting the 'green gap' to better absorb green and yellow light. Another opportunity is the absorption of far-red light, though it is poorer in energy (as it is of longer wavelength).

The usage of chlorophyll f (which absorbs far-red light) does allow plants to absorb light in the spectrum of 700nm-800nm, however incorporating it in plants is difficult and comes with other draw-downs, decreasing overall photosynthetic efficiency. However, the authors pointed out that by carefully designing the new photosynthetic units could preserve photosynthetic efficiency. (Mascoli, Bersanini, & Croce, 2020)

In *Synechococcus elongatus* PCC 7942, phycoerythrobilin (PEB) supply was tuned by modulating *pebA/pebB* expression to generate mutants with enhanced green-light harvesting; these mutants exhibited improved growth under green light. (Sato et al., 2024)

Most promisingly, shifting the ratio of chlorophyll a to chlorophyll b has increased leaf CO₂ fixation and starch and dry matter accumulation in tobacco plants. Chlorophyll a oxygenase (CAO) is involved in the synthesis of chlorophyll b, and its over-expression was linked to several positive indicators such as light absorption, electron transport efficiency, CO₂ assimilation. (Biswal et al., 2012)

6.2.3 Altering pigment concentration

Plants naturally compete with each other for resources, such as sunlight. This has made plants evolve more light-harvesting antenna complexes to be able to capture more photons. However, in agricultural settings, weeds are removed and plants can basically grow undisturbed. A higher concentration or bigger LHC's is detrimental to plants or leaves further down in the canopy. At full sunlight, plants absorb more light than they can use, leaving less light for leaves further down. Therefore, mutations that reduce the size of light-harvesting antenna complexes, called truncated light antenna (TLA) mutants, have been shown to improve yields at PSII by increasing light penetration deeper in the canopy.

The assembly of light-harvesting antennae depends on nuclear-encoded (ie. DNA is in nucleus) light-harvesting chlorophyll a and b binding proteins (LHCP's). Specifically, the process is mediated by chloroplast signal recognition pathway (CpSRP). This protein has been subject to further experiments. For example, the knock-down of CpSRP43 has been shown to increase the leaf to stem ratio in nicotiana tabacum, increasing its total biomass (Kirst, Gabilly, Niyogi, Lemaux, & Melis, 2018). Another mutation in rice reduced plant height while preserving grain mass (Lv et al., 2015). Plants lacking CpFTSY and ALB3 (other actors in the assembly of LHC's) have been shown to have severe growth and development problems (Durrett, Gassmann, & Rogers, 2006).

6.2.4 Overcoming photorespiration

It is estimated that photorespiration costs plants around 30% of the absorbed light energy. (Trafton, 2025)

An MIT group of chemists took a version of RuBisCo from a semi-anaerobic bacterium Gallionellaceae, which typically lives in low-oxygen environments. Exposing it to atmospheric levels of oxygen created evolutionary pressure and three different mutations were identified which improved RuBisCo's resistance to oxygen. Looking at these mutations can help understand how to improve CO₂ selectivity and shows that reducing this effect is indeed possible.

6.2.5 Synthetic carbon fixation pathways (e.g., CETCH cycle, implementing C4 in C3 plants)

The CETCH cycle is a synthetic alternative to the Calvin-Benson cycle. It contains 17 different enzymes, coming from six different species. It shows 20 times higher carbon fixation rate (faster) and requires 20% less energy. This makes it a very promising alternative to the CBC, however incorporating it into plants is difficult. (Schwander, von Borzyskowski, Burgener, Cortina, & Erb, 2016)

6.3 Applications

6.3.1 Higher yield in food and feed crops and nutritional make-up

This aspect was already discussed earlier, and it is probably the most impactful. 733 million people experience hunger (according to the WHO) worldwide, and improved photosynthesis can translate into increased crop production. Biotechnological improvements can aim to generally enhance the rate of photosynthesis (for example by improving electron transport, CO₂ fixation, or photoprotection). Alternatively, they can aim to increase the biomass of a given plant or how much crop it yields under realistic field conditions. In addition, the nutritional make-up of harvested organs can be altered, for example to increase protein content (as was examined by increasing RuBisCo content by Madalena Gració et al. in 2023). These improvements could very well save lives and show the potential of improved photosynthetic ability in plants. (World Health Organization, 2024; Gració et al., 2023)

6.3.2 Side-effect of improving research beneficial to other fields of science

Beyond direct agricultural outputs, research on engineering photosynthetic metabolism can also enable broader scientific and technological progress. Methods and delivery systems developed for plants can be transferred to other biotechnological fields, and high funding intensity in this area (due to expected profits by the food industry) can accelerate tool development that benefits related research communities. (Schulman, 2001)

6.3.3 Water-limited agriculture

Another application of improved photosynthesis can be increased water-use efficiency. Another perspective on engineering more efficient photosynthesis is therefore to limit H₂O consumption for the same amount of biomass produced. This is especially relevant because regions facing water scarcity are often also those with strong pressure on food supply. Improving water-use efficiency could allow cultivation in more arid regions, and stabilise yields under drought and heat stress.

6.3.4 Increased CO₂ capture for green cities and climate change

Improving photosynthesis efficiency can allow plants to assimilate more CO₂. This could show local benefits such as improved air quality and greener urban environments. However, it is likely to have no large direct impact on global warming, because achievable gains in CO₂ uptake per plant are limited, and the proportion of plants engineered for enhanced carbon assimilation would remain small compared to the global abundance of photosynthetic organisms.

6.4 Dangers and disadvantages

6.4.1 Gene flow

One disadvantage of genetic engineering is an environmental one: gene flow. Transgenes can spread via pollen or seeds to related crops or wild relatives, which can

then incorporate these genes into their own genome. This has ecological consequences and could contribute to the emergence of more persistent or competitive weeds if the introduced trait increases fitness in unmanaged environments. (Lu & Snow, 2005) Similarly, even the target plant which was initially genetically engineered could become invasive. If an engineered trait increases fitness under certain conditions, it could persist beyond cultivation and alter local species composition, potentially displacing non-engineered varieties or wild relatives. (World Health Organization, 2014)

The cultivation of herbicide-tolerant plants has been associated with the selection for herbicide-resistant weeds, making the weeds more tenacious against artificial herbicides, which can then lead to increased use, creating a vicious loop. (Green & Owen, 2010)

6.4.2 Antibiotic resistance

Historically, GM plants used antibiotic-resistance markers. This raises the concern that resistance genes could, under some circumstances, be transferred to microorganisms, including bacteria. This could become a health hazard if clinically relevant antibiotics become less effective because bacteria are more vastly exposed to them, which is why regulators have encouraged avoiding clinically relevant antibiotic markers where possible. Now, gene editing is mostly done using markers which are not relevant to medical antibiotic resistance. (European Food and Safety Authority, 2009)

6.4.3 Uncertainty over long-term effects

A second category of risks is uncertainty over long-term effects. Even when short-term toxicological and allergenicity assessments do not indicate harm, long time horizons and complex ecosystems make it difficult to fully exclude delayed or indirect effects (for example via food webs, soil microbiomes, or landscape-level biodiversity). This uncertainty is not an argument against res

6.5 Regulation on genetic engineering

6.5.1 EU environmental release framework

This EU law ensures that the cultivation and release of GMO's into the environment, as well as selling them on the market, requires approval after an environmental risk assessment.

(European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2001)

6.5.2 EU post-authorisation environmental monitoring

After being approved, GMO's must still undergo regular environmental monitoring and meet specific requirements.

(European Commission, n.d.)

6.5.3 EU 0.9% threshold

GM labelling is not required when the (authorised) GM material is below or equal to 0.9% per ingredient of a certain product, and the presence of it is technically unavoidable.

(European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003)

6.5.4 Gentechnikgesetz (Austria)

In Austria, laboratory and field research involving GMO's is primarily governed by the Genetic Engineering Act (Gentechnikgesetz, GTG), whose goal is to 'protect human health (including offsprings) and the environment from harms related to genetic engineering activities' (RIS - Rechtsinformationssystem, 2025a). Research in a 'closed system' is legally framed around organisational and technical measures that limit contact between GMO's and the public or the environment and prevent spreading. The GTG further requires that GMO work is carried out using measures that are wide-spread in any scientific undertaking, including appropriate treatment of wastewater, waste and exhaust air according to the relevant safety level. If a research project goes beyond contained use, for example experimental releases or field trials, it triggers separate permit and risk assessment requirements aligned with

EU rules on deliberate release (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2001; USP - Universitätssportplattform, 2025)

Before starting any research activity, the operator (typically the university or institute) must notify the authorities of first-time contained-use work with genetically modified micro-organisms in safety level 1 or 2. Depending on the activity type, the GTG sets waiting periods (for example 45 days for first-time safety level 1 or 2 work, with options to shorten when an internal biosafety committee has approved), while safety level 3 or 4 work may not begin until an explicit authorisation is granted. Research facilities must appoint a Biological Safety Officer with defined experience requirements and establish a Biological Safety Committee with specified composition rules, embedding biosafety oversight directly into how research is organised and approved internally. Competence is split by institutional context (universities and certain federal research bodies versus other operators), and higher-risk cases can be referred to scientific advisory bodies such as the WAGS, which influences how applications are assessed in practice (USP - Universitätssportplattform, 2025; RIS - Rechtsinformationssystem, 2025b).

6.5.5 Summary

These extensive laws go to show that the field is heavily regulated and monitored by legal structures, focusing on safety of its citizens, especially when GMO's are present in food.

6.6 Ethical discussion: genetic engineering and biotechnological innovation in photosynthesis

Engineering photosynthesis raises an ethical tension between beneficence (using technology to reduce suffering) and precaution (avoiding harms that are difficult to reverse). On the benefit side, applications such as yield gains, improved nutritional profiles, and improved water-use efficiency have a clear moral motivation because they target food insecurity and climate-related yield instability, where small productivity increases can save human lives. At the same time, the ethical justification for

deployment depends on whether these benefits are distributed fairly, rather than primarily going to a small number of patent holders. Concentration in seed and trait markets therefore becomes an ethical concern because it can create dependencies and limit farmer autonomy in regions that actually need a high crop diversity.

A second ethical axis is the effect on ecosystems and future generations. Risks such as gene flow, unwanted ecological effects, and uncertainty over the long term pose big problems because release into the environment is irreversible. Therefore, the relevant question is not whether genetic engineering is “safe”, but whether risks can be reduced to a level comparable to, or lower than, available alternatives (for example conventional breeding, pesticide-intensive practices, or land-use expansion). The EU deliberate release framework and post-authorisation monitoring put precaution into practice through external risk assessment and ongoing monitoring, aiming to ensure that deployment is backed by evidence and correctable if harms appear.

Finally, ethical acceptability depends on transparency and consent of the whole of society. Labelling, traceability, and clear communication influence whether consumers believe they have choice, which affects trust in research institutions and also the government. Even if a product meets safety standards, low transparency can undermine legitimacy and polarise public debate. In biotechnology, public resistance can slow adoption even of really beneficial inventions. Therefore, transparency and strong legislation are ethical instruments that are beneficial to both scientists and the wider public.

7 Conclusion

This pre-scientific paper clearly shows that highly complex chemical mechanisms (excitation energy transfer, oxygen-evolving complex, S-state cycle, cytochrome b_6f , FNR and the C3 mechanisms) underlie photosynthesis and that many steps in this process are to be better understood. With biotechnological innovation, photosynthesis can be enhanced in way to increase food production, generate fuel or capture CO₂ more efficiently. However, it must also be said that many approaches to increase artificial photosynthetic efficiency come with specific drawdowns and each method must be assessed individually.

In my opinion, Austrian legislation finds the right balance between enabling research in this field while also protecting its citizens from dangers, especially considering genetic engineering.

Through the writing of this pre-scientific paper, I have been able to deepen my understanding on many biochemical processes in relation to photosynthesis and genetic engineering. I have also learned how to approach complex scientific papers and quickly gain understanding in a new field, a skill that will certainly be helpful to me for my future.

References

- Albi, T., & Serrato, A. J. (2016). Sucrose synthesis and its regulation. *Plant Signaling & Behavior*, *11*(3), e1161877.
- Andersson, I. (1996). Large structures at high resolution: The 1.6 Å crystal structure of spinach ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase complexed with 2-carboxyarabinitol bisphosphate. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, *259*(1), 160–174.
- Armstrong, F. A., & Hirst, J. (2011). Reversibility and efficiency in electrocatalytic energy conversion and lessons from enzymes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *108*(34), 14049–14054.
- Ballicora, M. A., Iglesias, A. A., & Preiss, J. (2004). Adp-glucose pyrophosphorylase: a regulatory enzyme for plant starch synthesis. *Photosynthesis Research*, *79*(1), 1–24.
- Biswal, A. K., Kohli, A., Yoon, J.-M., Dufresne, C., Elich, T., Howe, G. A., ... Timko, M. P. (2012). Manipulation of light-harvesting antenna size alters photosynthetic carbon gain in arabidopsis. *Plant Molecular Biology*, *81*, 451–464.
- Blankenship, R. E. (2010). *Early evolution of photosynthesis* (Vol. 154) (No. 2). doi: 10.1104/pp.110.161687
- Blankenship, R. E. (2021). *Molecular mechanisms of photosynthesis* (3rd ed.). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Bock, R. (2015). Engineering plastid genomes: methods, tools, and applications in basic research and biotechnology. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, *66*, 211–241.
- Bombelli, P., Bradley, R. W., Scott, A. M., Philips, A. J., McCormick, A. J., Cruz, S. M., ... Fisher, A. C. (2011). Quantitative analysis of the factors limiting solar power transduction by synechocystis sp. pcc 6803 in biological photovoltaic devices. *Energy & Environmental Science*, *4*(11), 4690–4698.
- Brettel, K. (2001). Electron transfer and arrangement of the redox cofactors in photosystem i. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1507*(1-

- 3), 100–114.
- Brown, K. A., Wilker, M. B., Boehm, M., Dukovic, G., & King, P. W. (2012). Characterization of photochemical processes for h₂ production by cds nanorod-[fefe] hydrogenase complexes. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, *134*(12), 5627–5636.
- Bruns, C. M., & Karplus, P. A. (1995). Refined crystal structure of spinach ferredoxin reductase at 1.7 Å resolution: oxidized, reduced and 2'-phospho-5'-amp bound states. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, *247*(1), 125–145.
- Cardona, T., Sedoud, A., Cox, N., & Rutherford, A. W. (2012). Charge separation in photosystem ii: A comparative and evolutionary overview. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1817*(1), 26–43. doi: 10.1016/j.bbabi.2011.07.012
- Caspy, I., Schwartz, T., Bayro-Kaiser, V., Fadeeva, M., & Nelson, N. (2021). Structure of the plant photosystem i. *Nature Plants*, *7*, 1184–1192. doi: 10.1038/s41477-021-00959-9
- Cassan, N., Lagoutte, B., & Sétif, P. (2005). Ferredoxin-nadp⁺ reductase: the different functions of the two plastidic ferredoxins in electron transfer. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *280*(26), 25604–25611.
- Chen, M. T. L., & Whitney, S. M. (2023). Producing fast rubisco in tobacco to enhance photosynthesis. *Plant Physiology*.
- Cherepanov, D. A., Milanovsky, G. E., Petrova, A. A., Tikhonov, A. N., & Semenov, A. Y. (2017). Electron transfer through the acceptor side of photosystem i: Interaction with exogenous acceptors and molecular oxygen. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, *82*(11), 1249–1268. doi: 10.1134/S0006297917110037
- Croce, R., & van Amerongen, H. (2020). Light harvesting in oxygenic photosynthesis: Structural biology meets spectroscopy. *Science*, *369*(6506), eaay2058. doi: 10.1126/science.aay2058
- Dai, Z., Ku, M. S. B., & Edwards, G. E. (1993). C₄ photosynthesis: The co₂-concentrating mechanism and photorespiration. *Plant Physiology*, *103*(1), 83–90.
- Degen, G. E. (2023). Recent advances in cyclic electron flow around photosystem i.

- Current Opinion in Plant Biology*, 75, 102436.
- Degen, G. E., & Johnson, M. P. (2024). Regulation of cyclic electron flow in photosynthesis. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 75, copyright–year. (In press)
- Douch, A. (2022). *Understanding crispr-cas9*. YouTube video. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cLMo6DYdJRE>
- Durrett, T. P., Gassmann, W., & Rogers, E. E. (2006). The frd3-mediated efflux of citrate into the root vasculature is necessary for efficient iron translocation. *Plant Physiology*, 144(1), 197–205.
- Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc. (2026). *Chloroplast*. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/science/chloroplast> (Illustration)
- Encyclopedia of the Environment. (n.d.). *The path of carbon in photosynthesis*. Encyclopedia of the Environment. Retrieved from <https://www.encyclopedie-environnement.org/en/life/path-carbon-photosynthesis/> (Accessed February 11, 2026)
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Post-authorisation environmental monitoring of gmos*. European Commission website. Retrieved from https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/genetically-modified-organisms/post-authorisation_en
- European Food and Safety Authority. (2009). Use of antibiotic resistance genes as marker genes in genetically modified plants. *EFSA Journal*, 7(6), 1034.
- European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2001, March 12). *Directive 2001/18/ec on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms*. Official Journal of the European Communities. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32001L0018>
- European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2003). *Regulation (ec) no 1829/2003 on genetically modified food and feed*. Official Journal of the European Union. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32003R1829>
- Fang, X., Kalathil, S., & Reisner, E. (2020). Semi-biological approaches to solar-to-

- chemical conversion. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 49(14), 4926–4952.
- Ferreira, K. N., Iverson, T. M., Maghlaoui, K., Barber, J., & Iwata, S. (2008). Architecture of the photosynthetic oxygen-evolving center. *Science*, 303(5665), 1831–1838.
- Fischer, K. (2011). The import and export business in plastids: Transport processes across the inner envelope membrane. *Plant Physiology*, 155(4), 1511–1519.
- Fromme, P. (2001). Structure and function of photosystem i. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 11(4), 456–463.
- Fromme, P., Jordan, P., & Krauß, N. (2003). Structure of photosystem i. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, 1507(1-3), 5–31.
- Fujishima, A., & Honda, K. (1972). Electrochemical photolysis of water at a semiconductor electrode. *Nature*, 238(5358), 37–38.
- Gai, P., Cai, R., Li, H., & Chen, X. (2020). Artificial photosynthesis: Turning solar energy into chemical fuels. *Chemistry - A European Journal*, 26, 8369–8384.
- GeeksforGeeks. (2025, July 23). *C3 and c4 pathways*. Retrieved 2026-02-13, from <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/biology/c3-and-c4-photosynthetic-pathways/>
- Geigenberger, P., & Stitt, M. (2000). Sucrose synthase catalyses a readily reversible reaction in vivo in developing potato tubers and other plant tissues. *Planta*, 189(3), 329–339.
- Gració, M., et al. (2023). Increasing rubisco content in plants. *Plant Biotechnology Journal*.
- Green, J. M., & Owen, M. D. K. (2010). Herbicide-resistant crops: utilities and limitations for herbicide-resistant weed management. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 59(11), 5819–5829.
- Gunner, M. R. (2009). Quinone binding and electron transfer in photosynthetic reaction centers. *Accounts of Chemical Research*, 42(8), 1119–1126.
- Hahn, A., Vonck, J., Mills, D. J., Meier, T., & Kühlbrandt, W. (2020). Structure, mechanism, and regulation of the chloroplast atp synthase. *Science*, 360(6491), eaat4318.
- He, X., Miginiac-Maslow, M., Sigalat, C., Keryer, E., & Haraux, F. (2000). Mecha-

- nism of activation of the chloroplast atp synthase. ph dependence and the role of the subunit. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 275(35), 26973–26980.
- Henke, M., & Buck-Sorlin, G. (2017). Computational modeling of photosynthesis. *Computing and Informatics*, 36(6), 1492–1522. doi: 10.4149/cai_2017_6_1492
- Hilgers, E. H., Schöttler, M. A., Mettler-Altmann, T., Krueger, S., Dörmann, P., Eicks, M., . . . Gowik, U. (2018). The combined loss of triose phosphate and xylose 5-phosphate/phosphate translocators leads to severe growth retardation and impaired photosynthesis in arabidopsis thaliana tpt/xpt double mutants. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1331.
- Höhner, R., Pribil, M., Herbstová, M., Lopez, L. S., Kunz, H.-H., Li, M., . . . Leister, D. (2020). Plastocyanin is the long-range electron carrier between photosystem ii and photosystem i in plants. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(26), 15354–15362.
- InVivo Biosystems. (2024). *Hdr vs nhej: Dna repair pathway comparison*. Retrieved 2026-02-13, from <https://invivobiosystems.com/crispr/hdr-vs-nhej/>
- Jasin, M., & Rothstein, R. (2013). Repair of strand breaks by homologous recombination. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology*, 5(11), a012740.
- Jensen, P. E., & Leister, D. (2014). Chloroplast evolution, structure and functions. *F1000Prime Reports*, 6, 40. doi: 10.12703/P6-40
- Johnson, G. N. (2011). Physiology of psi cyclic electron transport in higher plants. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, 1807(3), 384–389.
- Johnson, M. P. (2024). Photosynthesis in 2024: Understanding the calvin-benson cycle. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*.
- Kato, Y., & Noguchi, T. (2015). Redox properties and regulatory mechanisms of [mn]4ca cluster in photosynthetic water oxidation. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, 1847(1), 96–107.
- Kean, K. M., Kuo, N., & Karplus, P. A. (2018). Structural and mechanistic insights into the roles of the active site water in ferredoxin-nadp⁺ reductase catalysis. *Biochemistry*, 57(50), 6866–6874.
- Kent, M. (2000). *Advanced biology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Khan Academy. (n.d.). *Eukaryotic gene regulation*. Khan Academy. Retrieved from <https://www.khanacademy.org/science/biology/gene-regulation>
- Kirchhoff, H. (2004). Diffusion of molecules and macromolecules in thylakoid membranes. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1664*(1), 110–121.
- Kirst, H., Gabilly, S. T., Niyogi, K. K., Lemaux, P. G., & Melis, A. (2018). Photosynthetic antenna engineering to improve crop yields. *Planta*, *247*(5), 1009–1020.
- Klauss, A., Haumann, M., & Dau, H. (2012). Alternating electron and proton transfer steps in photosynthetic water oxidation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *109*(40), 16035–16040.
- Kornienko, N., Zhang, J. Z., Sakimoto, K. K., Yang, P., & Reisner, E. (2018). Interfacing nature’s catalytic machinery with synthetic materials for semi-artificial photosynthesis. *Nature Nanotechnology*, *13*, 890–899.
- Kärkäs, M. D., Verho, O., Johnston, E. V., & Åkermark, B. (2014). Artificial photosynthesis: molecular systems for catalytic water oxidation. *Chemical Reviews*, *114*(24), 11863–12001.
- Lakshmi, K. V., Reifler, M. J., Chisholm, D. A., Wang, J.-Y., Diner, B. A., & Brudvig, G. W. (1999). Correlation of the cytochrome b559 content with the light saturation of electron transfer in photosystem ii. *Photosynthesis Research*, *59*, 143–151.
- Lamb, J. J., et al. (2022). Oxygenic photosynthesis. In *Hydrogen, biomass and bioenergy: Integration pathways for renewable energy applications* (pp. 21–53). Elsevier.
- Lambers, H., & Bassham, J. A. (2025). *Photosynthesis*. Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/science/photosynthesis> (Accessed February 11, 2026)
- Lambreva, M. D., Russo, D., Polticelli, F., Scognamiglio, V., Antonacci, A., Zobnina, V., ... Rea, G. (2014). Structure/function/dynamics of photosystem ii plastoquinone binding sites. *Current Protein & Peptide Science*, *15*(4), 285–295.

- Lewis, N. S., & Nocera, D. G. (2006). Powering the planet: Chemical challenges in solar energy utilization. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *103*(43), 15729–15735.
- Li, H., Nakajima, Y., Nomura, T., Kawakami, K., & Shen, J.-R. (2024). Structure of photosystem ii supercomplex with light-harvesting antenna from a red alga. *Nature Communications*, *15*, 1–12. doi: 10.1038/s41467-024-45689-9
- Lu, B.-R., & Snow, A. A. (2005). Gene flow from genetically modified rice and its environmental consequences. *BioScience*, *55*(8), 669–678.
- Lv, Y., Guo, Z., Li, X., Ye, H., Li, X., & Xiong, L. (2015). New insights into the genetic basis of natural chilling and cold shock tolerance in rice by genome-wide association analysis. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, *39*(3), 556–570.
- Malone, L. A., Proctor, M. S., Hitchcock, A., Hunter, C. N., & Johnson, M. P. (2021). Cytochrome b6f - orchestrator of photosynthetic electron transfer. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1862*(5), 148380. (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) doi: 10.1016/j.bbabi.2021.148380
- Mammoser, H., & Happe, T. (2023). The role of plastocyanin and cytochrome c6 in photosynthetic electron transport. *Photosynthesis Research*, *156*, 177–194.
- Mandal, M., Saito, K., & Ishikita, H. (2019). Redox potential of the oxygen-evolving complex in the electron transfer cascade of photosystem ii. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, *123*(49), 10329–10337.
- Martins, M. C. M., Hejazi, M., Fettke, J., Steup, M., Feil, R., Krause, U., . . . Lunn, J. E. (2013). Feedback inhibition of starch degradation in arabidopsis leaves mediated by trehalose 6-phosphate. *Plant Physiology*, *163*(3), 1142–1163.
- Mascoli, V., Bersanini, L., & Croce, R. (2020). Far-red absorption and light-use efficiency trade-offs in chlorophyll f photosynthesis. *Nature Plants*, *6*, 1044–1053.
- McCormick, A. J., Bombelli, P., Scott, A. M., Philips, A. J., Smith, A. G., Fisher, A. C., & Howe, C. J. (2011). Photosynthetic biofilms in pure culture harness solar energy in a mediatorless bio-photovoltaic cell (bpv) system. *Energy & Environmental Science*, *4*(11), 4699–4709.
- Mirkovic, T., Ostroumov, E. E., Anna, J. M., van Grondelle, R., Govindjee, &

- Scholes, G. D. (2017). Light absorption and energy transfer in the antenna complexes of photosynthetic organisms. *Chemical Reviews*, *117*(2), 249–293. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00002
- Nawrocki, W. J., Bailleul, B., Picot, D., Cardol, P., Rappaport, F., Wollman, F.-A., & Joliot, P. (2019). The mechanism of cyclic electron flow. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1860*(6), 433–438.
- Olson, J. M. (2004). The evolution of photosynthesis. *Photosynthesis Research*, *80*, 373–386. doi: 10.1023/B:PRES.0000030457.06495.83
- OpenStax. (2018). *Biology 2e*. Houston, TX: OpenStax. (Licensed under CC BY 4.0)
- Pfister, B., & Zeeman, S. C. (2016). Formation of starch in plant cells. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, *73*(14), 2781–2807.
- RIS - Rechtsinformationssystem. (2025a, July 19). *Gentechnikgesetz (gtg) - austrian genetic engineering act*. RIS. Retrieved from <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/>
- RIS - Rechtsinformationssystem. (2025b, June 3). *Gtg biological safety officer requirements*. RIS.
- Sander, & Joung. (2014). Crispr-cas systems for editing, regulating and targeting genomes. *Nature Biotechnology*.
- Sato, M., Sano, R., Yamazaki, S., Kawachi, M., Kumazawa, Y., Takaichi, S., & Miyashita, H. (2024). Tuning phycoerythrobilin supply enhances green-light absorption in *synechococcus elongatus*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*.
- Schulman, A. H. (2001). Molecular markers to assess genetic diversity. *Euphytica*, *118*(2), 115–130.
- Schwander, T., von Borzyskowski, L. S., Burgener, S., Cortina, N. S., & Erb, T. J. (2016). A synthetic pathway for the fixation of carbon dioxide in vitro. *Science*, *354*(6314), 900–904.
- Shevela, D., & Eaton-Rye, J. J. (2021). Photosystem ii and the unique role of bicarbonate: A historical perspective. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1862*(4), 148366. doi: 10.1016/j.bbabi.2020.148366
- Sirohiwal, A., Neese, F., & Pantazis, D. A. (2023). Protein matrix control of reaction

- center excitation in photosystem ii. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, *115*, 1326–1335. doi: 10.1021/jacs.2c11097
- South, P. F., Cavanagh, A. P., Liu, H. W., & Ort, D. R. (2019). Synthetic glycolate metabolism pathways stimulate crop growth and productivity in the field. *Science*, *363*(6422), eaat9077.
- Suganami, M., Suzuki, Y., Sato, T., & Makino, A. (2021). Relationship between rubisco activase and rubisco contents in transgenic rice with overproduced or decreased rubisco content. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, *67*(2), 217–226.
- Symington, L. S. (2016). Mechanism and regulation of dna end resection in eukaryotes. *Critical Reviews in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, *51*(3), 195–212.
- Tamang, S. (2023, September 13). *Atp synthase: Structure, mechanism, significances*. Retrieved 2026-02-13, from <https://microbenotes.com/atp-synthase/>
- Torella, J. P., Gagliardi, C. J., Chen, J. S., Bediako, D. K., Colón, B., Way, J. C., ... Nocera, D. G. (2015). Efficient solar-to-fuels production from a hybrid microbial-water-splitting catalyst system. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *112*(8), 2337–2342.
- Trafton, A. (2025). *Mit chemists tune rubisco to reduce photorespiration*. MIT News.
- University of Chicago. (2022, September). *The origin of life on earth, explained*. news.uchicago.edu. Retrieved from <https://news.uchicago.edu/explainer/origin-life-earth-explained> (Accessed February 11, 2026)
- USP - Universitätssportplattform. (2025, January 20). *Biosafety regulations for contained use*.
- Vogt, L., Vinyard, D. J., Khan, S., & Brudvig, G. W. (2015). Oxygen-evolving complex of photosystem ii: An analysis of second-shell residues and hydrogen-bonding networks. *Current Opinion in Chemical Biology*, *25*, 152–158. doi: 10.1016/j.cbpa.2014.12.040
- Webber, A. N., & Lubitz, W. (2001). P700: the primary electron donor of photosystem i. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*, *1507*(1-3), 61–79.

- Whitmarsh, J., & Govindjee. (2002). *Photosynthesis*.
- World Health Organization. (2014). *Frequently asked questions on genetically modified foods*. WHO website. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/food-genetically-modified>
- World Health Organization. (2024). *World hunger statistics*. WHO website. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news/item/24-07-2024-hunger-numbers-stubbornly-high-for-three-consecutive-years-as-global-crises-deepen--un-report>
- Wu, D., Hu, X., & Liu, M. (2025). Structural basis of plastocyanin-mediated electron transfer in photosynthesis. *Plant Physiology*.
- Xiong, J., Fischer, W. M., Inoue, K., Nakahara, M., & Bauer, C. E. (1998). Molecular evidence for the early evolution of photosynthesis. *Science*, *289*(5485), 1724–1730. doi: 10.1126/science.289.5485.1724
- Yamamoto, H., & Shikanai, T. (2018). Pgr5-dependent cyclic electron flow protects photosystem i under fluctuating light at donor and acceptor sides. *Plant Physiology*, *179*(2), 588–600.
- yourgenome.org. (n.d.). *What is rna splicing?* yourgenome.org. Retrieved from <https://www.yourgenome.org/facts/what-is-rna-splicing>

List of Figures

1	Graphical overview of noncyclic and cyclic electron transfer in chloroplasts	4
2	Molecular structures of chlorophyll	6
3	Absorption spectrum and action spectrum (actual photochemical efficiency) of major photosynthetic pigments	7
4	Oxygen-evolving complex and S-state cycle	14
5	The proton motive Q-cycle of cytochrome b_6f	18
6	ATP synthase structure and proton-driven rotation	25
7	C3, C4 and CAM carbon fixation strategies	27
8	Calvin-Benson cycle overview (1/2)	32
9	Calvin-Benson cycle overview (2/2)	33
10	Graphical simplification of the chloroplast	39
11	HDR vs NHEJ repair pathways	49

Adrien Reiser
Resselstraße 14

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Ich erkläre, dass ich diese vorwissenschaftliche Arbeit eigenständig angefertigt und nur die im Literaturverzeichnis angeführten Quellen benutzt habe.

Villach, February 16, 2026

.....

Unterschrift Adrien Reiser